

CHAPTER ONE

INTRODUCTION

1.0 BACKGROUND OF STUDY

Diabetes mellitus is defined as a metabolic disorder of multiple aetiology characterized by chronic hyperglycemia with disturbances of carbohydrate, protein and fat metabolism resulting from defects in insulin secretion, insulin action, or both (American Diabetes Association, 2011). It is due to the failure in the formation of insulin or liberation or action (Charles, 1962). The vast majority of cases of diabetes fall into two broad etiopathogenetic categories which are in one category. Type 1 diabetes mellitus, an autoimmune disease, is characterized by the loss of pancreatic β -cells the cause is an absolute deficiency of insulin secretion resulting in absolute insulin deficiency. It accounts for about 5-10% of all newly diagnosed diabetes mellitus (American Diabetes Association, 2011). Individuals at increased risk of developing this type of diabetes can often be identified by serological evidence of an autoimmune pathologic process occurring in the pancreatic islets and by genetic markers. In the other, much more prevalent category Type 2 diabetes (Dineshkumar *et al.*, 2010) the cause is a combination of resistance to insulin action and an inadequate compensatory insulin secretory response characterized by insulin resistance and β -cell dysfunction. It remains the most common form of diabetes mellitus and constitutes about 90-95 % of all diabetes cases (American Diabetes Association, 2011). In the latter category, a degree of hyperglycemia is sufficient to cause pathologic and functional changes in various target tissues, but without clinical symptoms, may be present for a long period of time before diabetes is detected (Pradhan *et al.*, 2009). As of 2014, an estimated 387 million people have diabetes worldwide (International Diabetes Federation, 2014) with type 2

diabetes making up about 90% of the cases (Shlomo *et al.*, 2011). This is equal to 8.3% of the adult population, with equal rates in both women and men (Vos *et al.*, 2010) In the years 2012 to 2014, diabetes is estimated to have resulted in 1.5 to 4.9 million deaths per year (World Health Organisation, 2013; International Diabetes Federation, 2014). Diabetes at least doubles the risk of death (WORLD HEALTH ORGANISATION, 2013). The number of people with diabetes is expected to rise to 592 million by 2035 (International Diabetes Federation, 2014). Diabetes mellitus is accompanied by vascular disorders, which is relatively specific to diabetes, and caused primarily by hyperglycemia. Recent studies have reported that the various mechanisms accompanying hyperglycemia cause more oxidative damage (increased oxidative stress) in the blood and tissue of diabetic patients, as compared with healthy individuals. One of the major hypotheses proposed to explain the hyperglycemia-induced onset of diabetic complications is an increase in oxidative stress (Giugliano *et al.*, 1996; Creager *et al.*, 2003; Brownlee, 2001; Rosen *et al.*, 1998; Sheetz and King, 2001). Oxidative stress refers to a serious imbalance between reactive species production and antioxidant defenses (Halliwell and Gutteridge, 2007). It occurs due to an increased generation and/or reduced elimination of reactive species (RS) by the antioxidant defense system. Hyperglycemia increases oxidative stress, which contributes to the impairment of the main processes that fail during diabetes, insulin action and insulin secretion. In addition, antioxidant mechanisms are diminished in diabetic patients, which may further augment oxidative stress (Rains and Jains, 2011; Maritim *et al.*, 2003). Several studies have addressed the possible participation of dietary antioxidants, such as vitamins and flavonoids (Bláha *et al.* 2004; Dias *et al.* 2005) in ameliorating the diabetic state and retarding the development of diabetes complications (Sheikh-Ali *et al.*, 2011; Cuerda *et al.*, 2011). Nowadays, more than 80% of the world's population use plants as their primary source of medicinal agents

(Cordell, 2002) probably because of the high cost of Western pharmaceuticals. Traditional medicines are generally more acceptable as compared to synthetic medicines (Bent, 2004). Plant extracts are widely used to treat various kinds of diseases but in nature many plants synthesize toxic substances in order to defend it against infections, insects and herbivores (Demma *et al.*, 2009). It is also showed that some substances that are present in some medicinal plants are potentially toxic and carcinogenic (De sa Ferreira and Vargas, 1999) and some of it may have a genotoxic potential (Sohnl *et al.*, 1995; Basaram *et al.*, 1996; Romero-Jimenez *et al.*, 2005). The presence of mutagenic and antimutagenic effects of plants have been related to the presence of certain phytochemical substances in the plants itself (Zeiger, 2001). *Hydrocotyle bonariensis* Lam. (Apiaceae) is one of such plants, locally known as Pegaga Embun and valued for treating various kinds of diseases such as tuberculosis, relieving the pain of rheumatism and arthritis, to increase brain capacity and for longevity (Masoumian *et al.*, 2011). Previous study has been reported that this herb has its medicinal use as emetics, diuretics and laxatives (Evans, 1992). It has also been reported that the leaves of this plant contain alkaloids, flavonoids, tannins, phenolic compounds and saponins as bioactive components (Ajani *et al.*, 2009).

1.1 STATEMENT OF PROBLEM

There is no information on the activities of exogenous antioxidants and level of lipid peroxidation in diabetics with prolonged administration of *Hydrocotyle bonariensis*, thus this present study is designed to investigate the activities of glutathione and concentration of malondialdehyde in type 2 diabetic rat models before and after administration of *Hydrocotyle bonariensis*.

1.2 SIGNIFICANCE OF RESEARCH

This study will give insight to the use of *Hydrocotyle bonariensis* as a possible antioxidant, which could be used as a therapy to ameliorate the various complications of diabetes that results from oxidative stress.

1.3 OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY

The General Objective:

The general objective of the present work is to determine/investigate the effectiveness of *Hydrocotyle bonariensis* on the level of malondialdehyde and activities of glutathione in streptozotocin induced type 2 diabetes in rat models.

Specific objectives are;

1. Induce with streptozotocin and determine type 2 diabetes mellitus among wistar rats test subject.
2. To determine the proximate analysis composition of *Hydrocotyle bonariensis*.
3. To also evaluate the effect of *Hydrocotyle bonariensis* on level of malondialdehyde in streptozotocin induced diabetes.

1.4 RESEARCH DESIGN

The research design adopted for this study is the comparative study approach where, objectively selected antioxidant parameters and lipid peroxidation estimation were empirically compared among control, treated and untreated animal test subjects to determine the effect of *Hydrocotyle bonariensis* on streptozotocin induced type II diabetes in rat models.

CHAPTER TWO

2.0 LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 PATHOPHYSIOLOGY

Insulin is the principal hormone that regulates the uptake of glucose from the blood into most cells of the body, especially liver, muscle, and adipose tissue. Therefore, deficiency of insulin or the insensitivity of its receptors plays a central role in all forms of diabetes mellitus (American Diabetes Association, 2014). Insulin is released into the blood by beta cells (β -cells), found in the islets of Langerhans in the pancreas, in response to rising levels of blood glucose, typically after eating. Insulin is used by about two-thirds of the body's cells to absorb glucose from the blood for use as fuel, for conversion to other needed molecules, or for storage. Lower glucose levels result in decreased insulin release from the beta cells and in the breakdown of glycogen to glucose. This process is mainly controlled by the hormone glucagon, which acts in the opposite manner to insulin (Kim, 2012). If the amount of insulin available is insufficient, if cells respond poorly to the effects of insulin (insulin insensitivity or insulin resistance), or if the insulin itself is defective, then glucose will not be absorbed properly by the body cells that require it, and it will not be stored appropriately in the liver and muscles. The net effect is persistently high levels of blood glucose, poor protein synthesis, and other metabolic derangements, such as acidosis (Shoback, 2011). When the glucose concentration in the blood remains high over time, the kidneys will reach a threshold of reabsorption, and glucose will be excreted in the urine (glycosuria) This increases the osmotic pressure of the urine and inhibits reabsorption of water by the kidney, resulting in increased urine production (polyuria) and increased fluid loss. Lost

blood volume will be replaced osmotically from water held in body cells and other body compartments, causing dehydration and increased thirst (polydipsia) (Shoback, 2011).

2.1.0 PREVALENCE OF DIABETES

The health implications associated with chronic hyperglycemia effects its damage through damage to small vessels, referred to as microvascular diseases. Diabetes is also an important factor in accelerating the hardening and narrowing of the arteries (arthrosclerosis), leading to stokes, coronary heart diseases, and other blood vessels diseases. As of 2014, an estimated 387 million people have diabetes worldwide (International Diabetes Federation , 2014) with type 2 diabetes making up about 90% of the cases (Shlomo *et al.*, 2011). This is equal to 8.3% of the adult population, with equal rates in both women and men (Vos *et al.*, 2010) In the years 2012 to 2014, diabetes is estimated to have resulted in 1.5 to 4.9 million deaths per year (World Health Organisation, 2013; International Diabetes Federation ,2014).Diabetes at least doubles the risk of death (World Health Organisation,2013). The number of people with diabetes is expected to rise to 592 million by 2035 (International Diabetes Federation, 2014).The global economic cost of diabetes in 2014 was estimated to be \$612 billion USD (International Diabetes Federation, 2014). In the United States, diabetes cost \$245 billion in 2012 (American Diabetes Association, 2013). Globally, there are different prevalent levels varying from tribe to tribe, country to country. According to World health organization (World Health Organisation) more than 220 million people worldwide diabetes had in 2004.

- WHO projects that diabetes death will double between 2005 and 2030.
- Almost half of diabetes deaths occur in people under the age of 70 years.
- Almost 80% of diabetes deaths occur in low and middle-income countries.

2.1.1 TYPES OF DIABETES

The two main types of diabetes are classified primarily on the basis of their underlying pathophysiology (American Diabetes Association, 2011).

2.1.1.0 Type 1 diabetes: (β -cell destruction, usually leading to absolute insulin deficiency)

Immune-mediated diabetes. This form of diabetes, which accounts for only 5–10% of those with diabetes, previously encompassed by the terms insulin dependent diabetes, type 1 diabetes, or juvenile-onset diabetes, results from a cellular-mediated autoimmune destruction of the β -cells of the pancreas. Markers of the immune destruction of the β -cell include islet cell autoantibodies, autoantibodies to insulin, autoantibodies to GAD (GAD65), and autoantibodies to the tyrosine phosphatases IA-2 and IA-2 b. One and usually more of these autoantibodies are present in 85–90% of individuals when fasting hyperglycemia is initially detected. Also, the disease has strong HLA associations, with linkage to the DQA and DQB genes, and it is influenced by the DRB genes. These HLA-DR/ DQ alleles can be either predisposing or protective. In this form of diabetes, the rate of β -cell destruction is quite variable, being rapid in some individuals (mainly infants and children) and slow in others (mainly adults). Some patients, particularly children and adolescents, may present with ketoacidosis as the first manifestation of the disease. Others have modest fasting hyperglycemia that can rapidly change to severe hyperglycemia and/or ketoacidosis in the presence of infection or other stress. Still others, particularly adults, may retain residual β -cell function sufficient to prevent ketoacidosis for many years; such individuals eventually become dependent on insulin for survival and are at risk for ketoacidosis. At this latter stage of the disease, there is little or no insulin secretion, as manifested by low or undetectable levels of plasma C-peptide. Immune-mediated diabetes commonly occurs in childhood and adolescence, but it can occur at any age, even in the 8th and 9th years of life. Autoimmune

destruction of b-cells has multiple genetic predispositions and is also related to environmental factors that are still poorly defined. Although patients are rarely obese when they present with this type of diabetes, the presence of obesity is not incompatible with the diagnosis. These patients are also prone to other autoimmune disorders such as Graves' disease, Hashimoto's thyroiditis, Addison's disease, vitiligo, celiac sprue, autoimmune hepatitis, myasthenia gravis, and pernicious anemia.

2.1.1.1 Type 2 diabetes: (ranging from predominantly insulin resistance with relative insulin deficiency to predominantly an insulin secretory defect with insulin resistance) This form of diabetes, which accounts for ;90–95% of those with diabetes, previously referred to as non–insulin-dependent diabetes, type 2 diabetes, or adult-onset diabetes, encompasses individuals who have insulin resistance and usually have relative (rather than absolute) insulin deficiency At least initially, and often throughout their lifetime, these individuals do not need insulin treatment to survive. There are probably many different causes of this form of diabetes. Although the specific etiologies are not known, autoimmune destruction of b-cells does not occur, and patients do not have any of the other causes of diabetes. Abnormalities of fatty-acid metabolism are increasingly recognized as key components of the pathogenesis of the metabolic syndrome and type 2 diabetes (McGarry, 1992). Fat-feeding and raised levels of circulating free fatty acids (FFAs) are clearly sufficient to induce peripheral and hepatic insulin resistance (Ruderman, 1999). Accumulation of lipids inside muscle cells (Krssak, 1999) and specific increases in muscle long-chain fatty acyl-CoA content have been implicated in causing insulin resistance (Ruderman *et al.*, 1999). In addition, lipid accumulation within pancreatic islets has been proposed to impair insulin secretion (Unger, 1995). Most patients with this form of diabetes are obese, and obesity itself causes some degree of insulin resistance. Patients who are not obese by

traditional weight criteria may have an increased percentage of body fat distributed predominantly in the abdominal region. Ketoacidosis seldom occurs spontaneously in this type of diabetes; when seen, it usually arises in association with the stress of another illness such as infection. This form of diabetes frequently goes undiagnosed for many years because the hyperglycemia develops gradually and at earlier stages is often not severe enough for the patient to notice any of the classic symptoms of diabetes. Nevertheless, such patients are at increased risk of developing macrovascular and microvascular complications. Whereas patients with this form of diabetes may have insulin levels that appear normal or elevated, the higher blood glucose levels in these diabetic patients would be expected to result in even higher insulin values had their β -cell function been normal. Thus, insulin secretion is defective in these patients and insufficient to compensate for insulin resistance. Insulin resistance may improve with weight reduction and/or pharmacological treatment of hyperglycemia but is seldom restored to normal. The risk of developing this form of diabetes increases with age, obesity, and lack of physical activity. It occurs more frequently in women with prior GDM and in individuals with hypertension or dyslipidemia, and its frequency varies in different racial/ethnic subgroups. It is often associated with a strong genetic predisposition, more so than is the autoimmune form of type 1 diabetes. However, the genetics of this form of diabetes are complex and not clearly defined.

Other specific types of diabetes due to other causes, e.g., genetic defects in beta-cell function, genetic defects in insulin action, diseases of the exocrine pancreas (such as cystic fibrosis), and drug- or chemical-induced (such as in the treatment of HIV/AIDS or after organ transplantation) Gestational diabetes mellitus (GDM) (diabetes diagnosed during pregnancy that is not clearly overt diabetes).

2.1.2 SIGNS AND SYMPTOMS OF DIABETES MELLITUS

The most easily recognized symptoms of diabetes mellitus are secondary to hyperglycemia, glucosuria, and ketoacidosis (KA).

2.1.2.0 Hyperglycemia

Hyperglycemia alone may not cause obvious symptoms, although some children reports general malaise, headaches, and weakness. They may also appear irritable and become ill-tempered. The main symptoms of hyperglycemia are secondary to osmotic diuresis and glycosuria.

2.1.2.1 Glycosuria

This condition leads to increased urinary frequency and volume (e.g. polyuria), which is particularly troublesome at night (Nocturnal) and often leads to enuresis in a previously continent child.

2.1.2.2 Polydipsia

Increased thirst, which may be insatiable, is secondary to the osmotic diuresis causing dehydration.

2.1.2.3 Weight loss

Insulin deficiency leads to uninhibited gluconeogenesis causing breakdown of protein and fat. Weight loss may be dramatic, although the child's appetite usually remains good. Failure to thrive and wasting may be the first symptoms noted in an infant or toddler and may precede to frank hyperglycemia.

2.1.2.4 Ketoacidosis

It is caused by the buildup of ketoacidosis beta hydroxybutyrate and acetoacetate in the body, leading to acidosis and ketonuria. An immediate consequence is that the patient starts to breathe very rapidly and deeply because the nervous system response attempts to increase blood pH by expelling carbon dioxide. Ketoacidosis is rare in older people with type 2 diabetes and is more likely to be confined in period of acute stress or infection. It also develops if a patient does not comply with treatment and is newly diagnosed diabetes (Mera, 1997). Symptoms of Ketoacidosis Include: Severe Dehydration, Smell of Ketones, Acidotic Breathing (Kussmaul Respiration), Abdominal Pain, Vomiting, Drowsiness and Coma.

2.1.3 DIAGNOSIS

Glycated hemoglobin and Glucose tolerance test.

Diabetes mellitus is characterized by recurrent or persistent hyperglycemia, and is diagnosed by demonstrating any one of the following (WORLD HEALTH ORGANISATION, 1999)

- Fasting plasma glucose level ≥ 7.0 mmol/l (126 mg/dl)
- Plasma glucose ≥ 11.1 mmol/l (200 mg/dl) two hours after a 75 g oral glucose load as in a glucose tolerance test
- Symptoms of hyperglycemia and casual plasma glucose ≥ 11.1 mmol/l (200 mg/dl)
- Glycated hemoglobin (HbA_{1C}) ≥ 48 mmol/mol (≥ 6.5 DCCT %) (AMERICAN DIABETES ASSOCIATION, 2010).

Glycated hemoglobin is better than fasting glucose for determining risks of cardiovascular disease and death from any cause (Selvin *et al.*, 2010).

Table1: WORLD HEALTH ORGANISATION diabetes diagnostic criteria (WHO, 2006; Vijan, 2010).

Condition	2 hour glucose	Fasting glucose	HbA _{1c}	
			mmol/mol	DCCT %
Unit	mmol/l(mg/dl)	mmol/l(mg/dl)	mmol/mol	DCCT %
Normal	<7.8 (<140)	<6.1 (<110)	<42	<6.0
Impaired fasting glycaemia	<7.8 (<140)	≥ 6.1(≥110) & <7.0(<126)	42-46	6.0–6.4
Impaired glucose tolerance	≥7.8 (≥140)	<7.0 (<126)	42-46	6.0–6.4
Diabetes mellitus	≥11.1 (≥200)	≥7.0 (≥126)	≥48	≥6.5

2.1.4 PREVENTION

There is no known preventive measure for type 1 diabetes (World Health Organisation, 2013).

Type 2 diabetes can often be prevented by a person being a normal body weight, physical exercise, and following a healthy diet (World Health Organisation, 2013). Dietary changes known to be effective in helping to prevent diabetes include a diet rich in whole grains and fiber, and choosing good fats, such as polyunsaturated fats found in nuts, vegetable oils, and fish (Willi *et al.*, 2007). Limiting sugary beverages and eating less red meat and other sources of saturated fat can also help in the prevention of diabetes (Willi *et al.*, 2007). Active smoking is also

associated with an increased risk of diabetes, so smoking cessation can be an important preventive measure as well (Nathan, 2005).

2.1.5 TREATMENT AND MANAGEMENT OF DIABETES MELLITUS

There is currently no cure for diabetes. The condition however, can be managed so that patients can live a relatively normal life. Treatment of diabetes focuses on two goals: keeping blood glucose within normal range and preventing the development of long-term complications. Careful monitoring of diet, exercise, and blood glucose levels are as important as the use of insulin or oral medications in preventing complications in diabetes.

2.1.5.0 ANTIDIABETIC AGENTS

Diabetes mellitus is a chronic disease that causes serious health complications and it is now one of the most common non-communicable diseases globally (World Health Organisation, 2012). It is the fourth or fifth leading cause of death in most high-income countries and there is substantial evidence that it is epidemic in many economically developing and newly industrialized nations (American Diabetes Association, 2011). Type 2 insulin-resistant diabetes mellitus accounts for 90–95% of all diabetes (American Diabetes Association, 2011). The main force driving this increasing incidence is a staggering increase in obesity, the single most important contributor to the pathogenesis of diabetes (Alkouri *et al.*, 2009; Verna and Berk, 2008). It is now clear that aggressive control of hyperglycemia in patients with type 2 diabetes can attenuate the development of chronic complications such as retinopathy, nephropathy and neuropathy (UKPDS, 1998). At present, therapy for type 2 diabetes relies mainly on several approaches intended to reduce the hyperglycemia itself: sulphonylureas (and related insulin secretagogues),

which increase insulin release from pancreatic islets; metformin, which acts to reduce hepatic glucose production; peroxisome proliferator-activated receptor-g (PPARg) agonists (thiazolidinediones), which enhance insulin action; α -glucosidase inhibitors, which interfere with gut glucose absorption; and insulin itself, which suppresses glucose production and augments glucose utilization. These therapies have limited efficacy, limited tolerability and significant mechanism-based side effects. Of particular concern is the tendency for most treatments to enhance weight gain. Several current approaches are also associated with episodes of hypoglycemia, and few of the available therapies adequately address underlying defects such as obesity and/or insulin resistance. A problem particular to the sulphonylureas is that many patients who respond initially become refractory to treatment over time. Thus, newer approaches are desperately needed. Particular emphasis should be placed on finding and using mechanisms that are dependent on physiological responses (for example, glucose-mediated insulin secretagogues), and that result in weight loss (or lack of weight gain). There is an unprecedented range of molecular drug targets within these pathways. They have been identified on the basis of predicted roles in modulating one or more key aspects of the pathogenesis of diabetes and metabolic syndrome. Several mechanistic categories for new therapeutic approaches can be considered. **First** are approaches aimed at reducing excessive glucose production by the liver; **Second**, mechanisms to augment glucose-stimulated insulin secretion; **Third**, specific molecular targets in the insulin signalling pathway; and **Fourth**, new approaches to obesity and altered lipid metabolism, which offer the prospect of net improvements in insulin action.

2.1.5.1 CLASSIFICATION OF ANTIDIABETIC AGENTS

In the United States, 11 classes of medications are approved for management of DM; these include 8 oral agents such as – biguanides, sulphonylureas, meglitinides, thiazolidinediones

(glitazones), alphaglucoSIDase inhibitors, DPP-4 inhibitors, bile acid sequestrants, dopamine-2 agonists, and 3 injectable agents such as – GLP-1 receptor agonists (incretins), amylin analogues and insulin.(American Diabetes Association,2012; Alexander *et al.*, 2008) The 18th WHO expert committee on the selection and use of essential medicines in 2011 requested a review of the current oral hypoglycemic medicines for use in adult to determine if updates to the essential medicine list (EML) are needed (World Health Organisation, 2011).Currently, the EML contains two oral hypoglycemics, glibenclamide (sulfonylurea) and metformin.

2.1.6 SURGERY

Transplantation of a healthy pancreas into a diabetic patient is a successful treatment; however, this transplant is usually done only if a kidney transplant is performed at the same time.

Although a pancreas transplant is possible, it is still not clear if the potential benefits outweigh the risks of the surgery and drug therapy needed.

2.1.7 ALTERNATIVE TREATMENT

Since diabetes can be life-threatening if not properly managed, patients should not attempt to treat this condition without medical supervision. A variety of alternatives therapies can be helpful in managing the symptoms of diabetes and supporting people with the disease.

Acupuncture can help relieve the pain associated with diabetic neuropathy by stimulation of certain points. Herbal remedies also may be helpful in managing diabetes. Although there is no herbal substitute for insulin, some herbs may help adjust blood sugar levels or manage other diabetic symptoms (Guigliano *et al.*, 1996). There has been a growing interest in antidiabetic agents from natural products especially those derived from plants. The antidiabetic agents have

been focused on plants used in traditional medicine because that may be a better treatment than currently used synthetic drugs.

2.2 DIABETES COMPLICATION

Hyperglycemia is the responsible of the development of diabetes complications as well.

Hyperglycemia damage is produced in cells in which glucose uptake is independent of insulin, which, similarly to what happens in beta-cells, explains that the cause of the complications resides inside the cells (Brownlee, 2001). Prolonged exposure to high glucose levels, genetic determinants of susceptibility and accelerating factors such as hypertension and dyslipidemia participate in the development of diabetic complications. Moreover, the development and progression of damage is proportional to hyperglycemia, which makes the lowering of glucose levels the most important goal for preventing complications and treating diabetes. The main tissues affected by diabetes complications at the microvasculature levels are retina, renal glomerulus, and peripheral nerves. Diabetes is also associated with accelerated atherosclerotic disease affecting arteries that supply the heart, brain, and lower extremities. In addition, diabetic cardiomyopathy is a major diabetic complication (Giacco and Brownlee, 2010).

2.3 OXIDATIVE STRESS AND DIABETES MELLITUS.

Increasing evidence suggests that oxidative stress plays a role in the pathogenesis of diabetes mellitus and its complications (Brownlee, 2001). Hyperglycemia increases oxidative stress, which contributes to the impairment of the main processes that fail during diabetes, insulin action and insulin secretion. In addition, antioxidant mechanisms are diminished in diabetic patients, which may further augment oxidative stress (Rains and Jains, 2011; Maritim *et al.*, 2003). Several studies have addressed the possible participation of dietary antioxidants, such as

vitamins, in ameliorating the diabetic state and retarding the development of diabetes complications (Sheikh-Ali *et al.*, 2011; Cuerda *et al.*, 2011) and flavonoids (Bláha *et al.* 2004; Dias *et al.* 2005). Whenever a cell's internal environment is perturbed by infections, disease, toxins or nutritional imbalance, mitochondria diverts electron flow away from itself, forming reactive oxygen species (ROS) and reactive nitrogen species (RNS), thus lowering oxygen consumption. This "oxidative shielding" acts as a defense mechanism for either decreasing cellular uptake of toxic pathogens or chemicals from the environment, or to kill the cell by apoptosis and thus avoid the spreading to neighboring cells (Naviaux, 2012). Therefore, ROS formation is a physiological response to stress. The term "oxidative stress" has been used to define a state in which ROS and RNS reach excessive levels, either by excess production or insufficient removal. Being highly reactive molecules, the pathological consequence of ROS and RNS excess is damage to proteins, lipids and DNA (Johansen *et al.*, 2005). Consistent with the primary role of ROS and RNS formation, this oxidative stress damage may lead to physiological dysfunction, cell death, pathologies such as diabetes and cancer, and aging of the organism (Ceriello, 2006). SOD is considered a first-line defense against ROS. This enzyme is present in nearly all cells, and converts $\bullet\text{O}_2$ into H_2O_2 . Mitochondrial and bacterial SOD contains Mn, while cytosolic SOD is a dimer containing Cu and Zn. As the H_2O_2 may still react with other ROS, it needs to be degraded by either one of the other two antioxidant enzymes, glutathione peroxidase (GSH-Px) or catalase (Johansen *et al.*, 2005; Fisher *et al.*, 2006). GSH peroxidase is located in the mitochondria. It catalyzes degradation of H_2O_2 by reduction, where two glutathione (GSH) molecules are oxidized to glutathione disulfide (GSSG). Regeneration of GSH by GSH-reductase requires NADPH, which is oxidized to NADP^+ . Catalase, on the other hand, is localized primarily in peroxisomes, and so it detoxifies the H_2O_2 that diffuses from the

mitochondria to the cytosol, converting it into water and molecular oxygen (Johansen *et al.*, 2005; Fisher, 2006). There are also nonenzymatic antioxidant mechanisms, which mostly help regenerate GSSG back into GSH.

Figure 1: The Antioxidant network and the generation of reactive species in diabetes. **Oxygen is converted to $\bullet\text{O}_2^-$ through activation of enzymatic and nonenzymatic pathways which is then dismutated to H_2O_2 by SOD. H_2O_2 can be converted to H_2O by catalase or glutathione peroxidase (GSH-Px) or to $\bullet\text{OH}$ after reaction with Cu or Fe. Glutathione reductase regenerates (GSH). In addition, $\bullet\text{O}_2^-$ reacts rapidly with $\bullet\text{NO}$ to form ONOO^- (Johansen *et al.*, 2005).**

Antioxidant vitamins such as A, C, E and alpha-lipoic acid are among these mechanisms.

Although all these antioxidant defenses work together to eliminate H_2O_2 (and thus superoxide)

from the cell, in the presence of reduced transition metals (Cu, Fe), H_2O_2 can be transformed into $\bullet OH$, which is a highly reactive ROS, by the Fenton reaction (Johansen *et al.*, 2005; Evans *et al.*, 2002). Oxidative stress caused by hyperglycemia in diabetes may impair insulin signaling, leading to insulin resistance. Although no mechanisms have been completely established, several responses to ROS excess in the insulin signaling have been proposed. Oxidative stress plays a pivotal role in the development of diabetes complications, both at the microvascular and macrovascular levels. Results derived from two of diabetes complications investigation point towards mitochondrial superoxide overproduction as the main cause of metabolic abnormalities of diabetes (Giacco and Brownlee, 2005). Recent studies have reported that the various mechanisms accompanying hyperglycemia cause more oxidative damage (increased oxidative stress) in the blood and tissue of diabetic patients, as compared with healthy individuals. In fact, Dandona *et al.* reported that increases in 8-hydroxydeoxyguanosine, content in monocytes considered to be an indicator of oxidative degeneration, are observed in monocyte DNAs of patients with type I diabetes mellitus (Dondona *et al.*, 1996) It is also reported that phospholipids in plasma lipoprotein undergo oxidative modification in patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus, leading to an increase in contents of peroxide lipids and lysophosphatidylcholine, (Takahara *et al.*, 1997) and that an accumulation of peroxide lipids is observed in cardiac and vascular tissues in diabetic animals (Nishio *et al.*, 1998). Enhanced oxidative stress in the blood and tissue is thought to play an important role in the onset and progression of atherosclerosis and microvascular complications in diabetic patients. Thus, the molecular mechanisms of the enhancement of oxidative stress in diabetes have been studied in two topics such as {1} increased production of active oxygen and {2} impaired antioxidant defense (function of scavengers).

2.3.0 Glycation and oxidation of proteins and lipids, and active oxygen production

Non-enzymatic glycation of proteins under hyperglycemic conditions is accompanied by the production of active oxygen. Using the electron paramagnetic resonance method, Mullarkey *et al.* demonstrated that non-enzymatic glycation of proteins under glucose abundant conditions is accompanied by superoxide anion ($\bullet\text{O}_2$) production (Mullarkey *et al.*, 1990) Under hyperglycemic conditions, intracellular concentrations of glucose and its metabolites are elevated, which is followed by the glycation of non-enzymatic proteins, leading to the formation of a glycation product, fructose-lysine (FL). Some of the FL are further degraded into 3-DG (3-deoxyglucosone), which undergoes additional oxidative degradation, resulting in the formation of CML (Nepsilon-(carboxymethyl) lysine). Furthermore, an additional oxidative crosslinking reaction may occur, leading to the formation of pentosidine and other advanced glycation end products (AGEs) (Fu *et al.*, 1996). Meanwhile, the oxidation of n-6 unsaturated fatty acids causes the formation of glyoxal, malondialdehyde, and 4-hydroxynonenal, which have carbonyl groups, in addition to that of glucose; these then react with the proteins around them, leading to the formation of glycooxidation products and lipoxidation products. This is described as “carbonyl stress.”(Baynes and Thorpe, 1999) These carbonyl compounds are also involved in the production of active oxygen and in the modification of cellular functions. Both CML and pentosidine, which are AGEs, increase with aging and in patients with diabetes mellitus (Dyer *et al.*, 1993).

2.3.1 Impairments of the Antioxidant Defense Mechanism Due to Hyperglycemia

1. Endogenous antioxidants

Endogenous antioxidants including ascorbate, vitamin E, reduced glutathione, carotene, various amino acids, proteins, uric acid, bilirubin, etc. directly scavenge active oxygen. Under hyperglycemic conditions, the intracellular concentrations of reduced ascorbate and of reduced glutathione and vitamin E are reported to be decreased (Giugliano *et al.*, 1996). Accordingly, it can be said that antioxidant supplementation is desirable in patients with diabetes mellitus.

2. Endogenous scavenger enzyme systems

the metabolic pathway comprising the enzyme system involved in the scavenging of active oxygen generated in cells. Such enzymes include the following: 1) Superoxide dismutase (SOD), the enzyme that converts endogenous O_2 into hydrogen peroxide, including Cu, Zn-SOD, Mn-SOD, and extracellular SOD; and 2) catalase and the glutathione redox cycle (GR cycle), which convert hydrogen peroxide (H_2O_2) into water. Hydrogen peroxide itself does not have an unpaired electron but is converted into a highly reactive hydroxyl radical ($\cdot OH$), and accordingly, hydrogen peroxide detoxification mechanism plays an important role in protecting cells and tissue from oxidative stress. The activity of the GR cycle is dependent on the activity of the enzymes participating in the cycle including glutathione peroxidase and glutathione reductase, on the intracellular contents of NADPH (reduced nicotinamide adenine dinucleotide phosphate), and on the activity of the pentose phosphate pathway, an NADPH regeneration system. Hyperglycemia has been reported to impair these antioxidant defenses (Kashiwagi *et al.*, 1994 Asahina *et al.*, 1995). Under hyperglycemic conditions, the SOD is glycosylated and the peptide chain is cut, resulting in a decrease in its activity. In addition, the activity of the GR cycle is decreased due to the impaired activation of the pentose phosphate pathway. The

antidiabetic agents have been focused on plants used in traditional medicine because that may be a better treatment than currently used synthetic drugs. Also the fact that none of the anti-diabetic drugs could give a long term glyceamic control without causing any adverse side effects such as : gastrointestinal (GI) disturbances with metformin, weight gain, gastrointestinal disturbances and liver injury with thiazolidinediones, gastrointestinal disturbances, weight gain and hypersensitivity reactions with meglitinides and flatulence, diarrhoea and abdominal bloating with alpha-glucosidase inhibitors. (Salim, 2005; Singh *et al.*, 2006). Hence, the search for drugs with low cost, more potential and with fewer side effects has become very imperative. Medicinal plants provide a useful source of oral hypoglycemic compounds for the development of new pharmaceutical as well as dietary supplement to existing therapies (Bailey and Day, 2002).

To date, herbs have remained useful not only as remedy for different diseases that affect humans and animals, but also as good starting points for the discovery of bioactive molecules for drug development. The scientific exploitation of herbs used ethno medicinally for pain relief, wound healing and abolishing fevers has resulted in the identification of a wide range of compounds that have been developed as new therapies for cancer, hypertension, diabetes etc. (Harvey 2008).

2.4 CHEMICAL METHOD OF INDUCTION OF DIABETES MELLITUS IN EXPERIMENTAL RATS (DIABETOGENS)

Experimental diabetes mellitus has been induced in laboratory animals by several methods that include: chemical, surgical and genetic (immunological) manipulations. Most experiment in diabetes is carried out in rodents, although some studies are still performed in larger animals (Rees and Alcolado 2005; Urban *et al.*, 2008). The majority of studies published in the field of ethnopharmacology between 1996 and 2006 employed chemical induced model. Streptozotocin

(STZ, 69% and alloxan (31%) are by far the most frequently used drugs and this model has been useful for the study of multiple aspects of the disease (Rydgren *et al.*, 2007). Both drugs exert their diabetogenic action when they are administered parenterally (intravenously, intraperitoneally or subcutaneously). The dose of these agents required for inducing diabetes depends on the animal species, route of administration and nutritional status (Balamurugan *et al.*, 2003). Alloxan, a well-known diabetogenic agent is widely used to induce type 2 diabetes in animals (Viana *et al.*, 2004). The drug and its reduction product dialuric acid establish a redox cycle with the formation of superoxide radicals. These radicals undergo dismutation to hydrogen peroxide. Thereafter, highly reactive hydroxyl radicals are formed by fenton reaction. The action of reactive oxygen species with a simultaneous massive increase in cytosolic calcium concentration causes rapid destruction of β -cells (Szkudelki, 2001). Thus alloxan induced diabetes mellitus served as a pathological biomodel for testing a substance with supposed antioxidant activities *in vivo* (Bartosikova *et al.*, 2003). One of the targets of the reactive oxygen species is DNA of pancreatic islets. Its fragmentation takes place in β - cells exposed to alloxan (Takasu *et al.*, 1991). The increase in oxygen free radicals in diabetic conditions is mainly because of the effect of the diabetogenic agent alloxan. With this method (Macedo *et al.*, 2005) induced diabetes mellitus in experimental rats. Although the use of chemical (alloxan and streptozotocin) to induce type 2 diabetes mellitus is the most widely used method, recently it has been widely criticized as being unsuitable because the chemical seems to destroy the β cells and create more of type 1 than type 2 diabetes (Masiello, 2006). Streptozotocin or Streptozocin or Izostazin or Zanosar (STZ) is a synthetic antineoplastic agent that is classically an anti-tumor antibiotic and chemically is related to other nitrosureas used in cancer chemotherapy. Streptozotocin sterile powders are provided and prepared as a chemotherapy agent. Each vial of

sterilized Streptozotocin powder contains 1gram of Streptozotocin active ingredient with the chemical name, 2-Deoxy-2-(((methylnitrosoamino)-carbonyl) amino)-D-glucopyranose and 200 milligram citric acid. Streptozotocin is available for intravenous use as a dry-frozen, pale yellow, sterilized product. Pure Streptozotocin has alkaline pH. When it is dissolved inside the vial in distilled water as instructed, the pH in the solution inside the vial will be 3.5-4.5 because of the

presence of citric acid.

Figure 2: Structure of Streptozotocin (Herr *et al.*, 1967).

2.5 MALONYLALDEHYDE AND GLUTATHIONE AS BIOMARKERS OF HYPERGLYCEMIA-INDUCED OXIDATIVE STRESS.

Malondialdehyde, MDA, is a highly reactive three carbon dialdehyde produced as a byproduct of polyunsaturated fatty acid peroxidation (Janero, 1990) and also during arachidonic acid metabolism for the synthesis of prostaglandins (Marnette, 1999). MDA can combine with several functional groups on molecules including proteins, lipoproteins, RNA and DNA (Sevilla, 1997). The monitoring of MDA levels in biological materials can be used as an important indicator of lipid peroxidation *in vitro* and *in vivo* for various diseases. Lipid peroxidation is a well-

established mechanism of cellular injury in both plants and animals and is used as an indicator of oxidative stress in cells and tissues. Lipid peroxides, derived from polyunsaturated fatty acids, are unstable and decompose to form a complex series of compounds, which include reactive carbonyl compounds, including MDA. MDA can be generated during cyclooxygenase (COX) catalysis in human platelets; formation from prostaglandin endoperoxide (PGH₂), catalyzed by thromboxane synthase (Diczfalusy *et al.*, 1977) and in liver cells (Plastaras *et al.*, 2000) by breakdown of PGH₂.

Figure 3: Conversion of prostaglandin endoperoxide (PGH₂) to 12-hydroxyheptadecatrienoate (HHT) and Malondialdehyde (Plastaras *et al.*, 2000).

It was suggested that the bulk of MDA in human plasma is bound to protein; this would explain the very low levels of MDA in plasma as measured under standard assay conditions (Lefevre *et al.*, 1996). Malondialdehyde reaction with Thiobarbituric acid is one of the most frequently used biomarker for free radical mediated damage (Janero *et al.*, 1990; Nielsen *et al.*, 1997). The measurement of MDA, which is the most abundant of lipid peroxidation products, is a convenient and sensitive method for quantitative estimation of lipid peroxide concentration in many types of samples including drugs, food products and biological tissues from human and animal. The most common method of measuring MDA is based on the reaction with thiobarbituric acid (TBA). The thiobarbituric acid reactive substances (TBARS) assay is the

colorimetric method widely used for the detection of lipid peroxidation in biological materials. MDA is formed as a result of lipid peroxidation and reacts with thiobarbituric acid under high temperature (90-100°C) and acidic condition. The reaction yields a pink MDA-TBA adduct, the product of 2 mol of TBA plus 1 mol of MDA, the colored complex can be extracted into organic solvents such as butanol and measured by fluorometry or spectrophotometry using wavelength 532 nm with an extinction coefficient $\epsilon_{532} = 1.53 \times 10^5 \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ (Nair and Turner, 1984).

Figure 4: Thiobarbituric acid reaction (Ge´rard-Monnier *et al.*, 1997).

2.6 MEDICINAL PLANTS,

Plants are endowed with various phytochemical molecules such as vitamins, terpenoids, phenolic acids, lignins, stilbenes, tannins, flavonoids, quinones, coumarins, alkaloids, amines, betalains, and other metabolites, which are rich in antioxidant activity (Zheng and Wang, 2001; Cai *et al.*, 2003). Studies have shown that many of these antioxidant compounds possess anti-inflammatory, antiatherosclerotic, antitumor, antimutagenic, anticarcinogenic, antibacterial, and antiviral activities (Sala *et al.*, 2002; Rice-Evans *et al.*, 1995). The ingestion of natural antioxidants has been associated with reduced risks of cancer, cardiovascular disease, diabetes, and other diseases associated with ageing (Ashokkumar *et al.*, 2008; Veerapur *et al.*, 2009) and in recent years, there has been a worldwide trend towards the use of the natural phytochemicals

present in berry crops, teas, herbs, oilseeds, beans, fruits and vegetables (Kitts *et al.*, 2000; Wang and Jiao., 2000).

2.7 *Hydrocotyle Bonanriensis*, a medicinal plant

Hydrocotyle bonanriensis(Lam) plant popularly called Water pennywort or dollarweed is locally known as *Pegaga Embun* is a perennial prostrate herb and is found mostly in tropical and subtropical regions of the world (Vimala *et al.*, 2003). It is a rhizomatous perennial herb common to the barrier islands of Southern United states and valued for treating various kinds of diseases such as tuberculosis, relieving the pain of rheumatism and arthritis, to increase brain capacity and for longevity (Masoumian *et al.*, 2011). Previous study has been reported that this herb has its medicinal use as emetics, diuretics and laxatives (Evans, 1992). Besides that, studies done by Edeoga *et al.*, (2005) showed that, leave of the plant is rapidly gaining popularity by some local people in Western Nigeria because it can treat various symptoms of ophthalmic diseases. It has also been reported that the leaves of this plant contain alkaloids, flavonoids, tannins, phenolic compounds and saponins as bioactive components (Ajani *et al.*, 2009). These phytochemicals have been reported to act as better antioxidants than the classical ones (Narayan and Venkataramam, 2002). Dietary modification is the simplest and cheapest form of diabetes treatment and is even the clinically recommended primary therapy in type 2 diabetes (Mshelia *et al.*, 2005). Many specific interventions have been carried out in the management and perhaps prevention of diabetes and one of the integral components is medical nutrition. Whether for management or prevention of diabetes and its complications the purpose of nutrition recommendation is the underlying concern for optimal nutrition through healthy food choices and an active lifestyle (Ntui *et al.*, 2006).

2.8 SCIENTIFIC CLASSIFICATION OF *Hydrocotyle bonariensis*.

Kingdom: *Plantae*

Phylum: *Magnoliophyta*

Class: *Magnoliopsida*

Order: *Apiales*

Family: *Araliaceae*

Subfamily: *Hydrocotyloideae*

Genus: *Hydrocotyle*

Species: *Bonariensis Lam.*

Common names: Water pennywort, dollarweed.

2.8.0 DESCRIPTION

It has numerous white to creamy yellow flowers; flower stalk can be 30cm (12inches). It produces a dry dehiscent fruit that at maturity splits two or more parts each with a single seed. Leaves solitary at each node, simple, peltate (shaped like a shield having the stalk or support attached to the lower surface rather than at or near the margin); lamina are mostly 30-120mm in diameter., shallowly lobed, margins or lobes crenate, lamina fleshy, glabrous; petiole are mostly 15cm long; stipules are scarious, 2-4mm long. Umbels compound, many flowered with 1-6cm; spikes and clustered at the base of the rays; peduncle is usually about 40cm long, but usually longer than the leaves; pedicels are 2-20mm long. Fruits are transversely ellipsoid, 1.5-2mm

long, 2.5-3mm wide, base and apex emarginated; dorsal and lateral ribs are prominent. Fruits of *Hydrocotyle bonariensis* are ovoid in lateral view, they are strongly compressed laterally, light brown and are about 2.2mm long, 2.6mm wide and 0.8mm thick, the median and lateral ribs are prominent. The mericarp surface is smooth and the epidermal cells contain tanniferous substances. Mesocarp is of 6-20 rows of cells; the outer is 6-8 rows parenchymatous and flattened preclinically, the inner is 5-12 rows present in the ribs and slightly lignified. Endocarp is of 2 rows of fiber-like sclerieds, and the cells of the innermost layers are arranged longitudinally. The vascular bundles are 5 in each mericarp and are very small. Intrajugal oil ducts are associated with each bundle. Crystals in the innermost layer of mesocarp are adjacent to the endocarp not forming an ontinous layer. Ventral bundles are absent.

Figure 5: Leaves of *Hydrocotyle bonanriensis*.

2.9 PHYTOCHEMICALS

Phytochemicals are defined as the substances found in edible fruits and vegetables that exhibit a potential for modulating human metabolism in a manner beneficial for the prevention of chronic and degenerative diseases (Tripoli *et al.*, 2007). Phenolics are defined as a class of polyphenols which are important secondary metabolites present in plants (Slade *et al.*, 2005) and are also responsible for their antioxidant action and various beneficial effects in a multitude of diseases (Hotta *et al.*, 2002; Williams *et al.*, 2004). Polyphenols are characterized as:

1. **Phenolic compounds:** Are aromatic organic compounds with at least one hydroxyl group attached directly to a benzene ring. These are hydroxylated derivatives of benzoic acid, present in form of esters and glycosides.
2. **Phenolic acids:** cinnamic acid derivatives. Often present in esterified form.
3. **Glycosidic phenylpropanoid esters** (Skerget *et al.*, 2005; Ferreira *et al.*, 2010). On the basis of C-skelton, polyphenols are classified as:
 - a. Flavonoids
 - b. Phenolic acids (Slade *et al.*, 2005)

2.9.0 flavonoids

Flavonoids are low molecular weight (Fernandez *et al.*, 2006; Heim *et al.*, 2002) bioactive polyphenols (Hollman and Katan, 1999) which play a vital role in photosynthesizing cells (Cushnie and Lamb, 2005). The original "flavonoid" research apparently began in 1936, when flavonoids are secondary metabolites characterised by flavan nucleus (Heim *et al.*, 2002) and C₆-C₈-C₆ carbon-skeleton (Peterson and Dwyer, 1998; Tsuchiya, 2010). These are group of structurally related compounds with a chromane-type skelton having phenyl substituent in C₂-C₃ position (Rijke *et al.*, 2006). The basic structural feature of flavonoid is 2-phenyl-benzo- γ -pyrane

nucleus consisting of two benzene rings (A and B) linked through a heterocyclic pyran ring. Flavonoids are widely distributed among the plant kingdom (Cushnie and Lamb, 2005). Flavonoids are found in vegetables, fruits, nuts, seeds, stem, flowers, tea, wine etc. These are an integral part of our daily diet (Cook and Samman, 1996; Sahu and Gray, 1996; Prey *et al.*, 2003). The dietary intake of flavonoids is estimated to be 1-2 g/day (Fernandez *et al.*, 2006). The average intake of flavonols and flavones was found to be 23 mg/day, among which, flavonol quercetin contributed 16 mg/day (Heim *et al.*, 2002). Flavonoids have been reported to exert wide range of biological activities. These includes: anti-inflammatory, antibacterial, antiviral, antiallergic (Cushnie and Lamb, 2005; Murray, 1998; Cook and Samman, 1996), cytotoxic antitumor, treatment of neurodegenerative diseases, vasodilatory action (Williams *et al.*, 2004; Murray, 1998; Tsuchiya, 2010; Chebil *et al.*, 2006). In addition flavonoids are known to inhibit lipid-peroxidation, platelet aggregation, capillary permeability and fragility, cyclo-oxygenase and lipoxygenase enzyme activities. They exert these effects as antioxidants, free radical scavengers, chelators of divalent cation (Cook and Samman, 1996; Chebil *et al.*, 2006; Middleton *et al.*, 2000). Flavonoids are powerful antioxidants against free radicals and are described as free-radical scavengers (Pal *et al.*, 2009). This activity is attributed to their hydrogen donating ability. Indeed, the phenolic groups of flavonoids serve as a source of a readily available ‘‘H’’ atoms such that the subsequent radicals produced can be delocalized over the flavonoid structure (Tripoli *et al.*, 2007). Free radical scavenging capacity is primarily attributed to high reactivities of hydroxyl substituents that participate in the reaction (Heim *et al.*, 2002). Flavonoids inhibit lipid peroxidation *in vitro* at an early stage by acting as scavengers of superoxide anion and hydroxyl radicals. They terminate chain radical reaction by donating hydrogen atom to a peroxy radical, thus, forming flavonoids radical, which, further reacts with

free radicals thus terminating propagating chain (Cook and Samman, 1996; Ferreira *et al.*, 2010). Quercetin is a flavonoid widely distributed in nature. The name has been used since 1857, and is derived from quercetum (oak forest), after Quercus. (Merriam-Webster, 2015; Encyclopedia Britannica, 2015). It is a naturally occurring polar auxin transport inhibitor. (Fisher *et al.*, 1997). Braca *et al.*, isolated several flavonoids from the leaves of *Licania licaniaeflora* and reported quercetin derivatives to possess strongest antioxidant activity and flavonone 8-hydroxy-naringen and kaempferol 3- O- α -rhamnoside possesses lowest antioxidant activity (Braca *et al.*, 2002). Salucci *et al.*, reported that dietary flavonoids like epicatechin, epigallocatechin, galate, gallic acid, quercetin-3-glucoside possess strong antioxidant activity (Salucci *et al.*, 2002). Gulati *et al.*, reported that quercetin at a dose of 15 mg/ 100g p.o. produced significant hepatoprotection (Jung *et al.*, 2010). Quercetin is abundantly found in human diet and it gets extensively metabolized during absorption in the small intestine and in the liver, and thus exerts a dose-dependent inhibitory effect on cell proliferation (Ramos, 2007). In addition, animal and *in vitro* studies have shown that tea catechins increase the activity of several detoxifying and antioxidant enzymes, such as glutathione reductase, glutathione peroxidase, glutathione S-reductase, catalase, and quinone reductase (Havsteen, 2002 ;Ramos, 2007). In estrogen-dependent tumor cells or animal models, this anti-proliferative effect has been related to the antiestrogenic properties of certain flavonoids (e.g., isoflavonoids, quercetin). Flavonones having sugar moiety showed antimicrobial activity while none of the flavonols and flavonolignans showed inhibitory activity on microorganisms. Quercetin has been reported to completely inhibit growth of *Staphylococcus aureus* (Tapas *et al.*, 2008). Quercetin, naringenin are reported to be inhibitors of *Bacillus subtilis*, *Candida albicans*, *Escherichia coli*, *Staphylococcus nervous*, *Staphylococcus epidermis*, *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* (Talab-Contini *et al.*, 2003).

2.9.1 Effect of flavonoids on diabetes mellitus: Etiology of diabetes mellitus: Diabetes

mellitus is a serious chronic disease. Effective control of the blood glucose level is a key step in preventing or reversing diabetic complications and improving the quality of life in both types 1 and 2 diabetic patients (Zhou *et al.*, 2009).

2.9.2 Flavonoids in treatment of diabetes mellitus:

All flavonoids cannot cure diabetes mellitus because most types of this disease are basically genetic and no single drug can correct an inborn error. However, flavonoids can ameliorate some of the consequences of diabetes mellitus (Havsteen, 2002). Flavonoids have been identified to be good inhibitors of aldose reductase (Patra and Chua, 2010). It has been reported by several researchers that quercetin possess antidiabetic activity and it has been found that it brings about regeneration of pancreatic islets and increases insulin release in streptozotocin induced diabetes. Also, it has been reported to stimulate Ca^{2+} uptake from isolated islet cells thus suggesting it to be effective even in non-insulin dependent diabetes (Tapas *et al.*, 2008). Li *et al.*, indicated that flavonoids in *Ipmoea batalas* leaf possesses antidiabetic activity against alloxaninduced diabetes at a dose of 100 mg/kg (Li *et al.*, 2009). Sriram *et al.*, reported fisetin to be a therapeutic agent for treatment of diabetes mellitus at a dose of 10 mg/kg (Sriram *et al.*, 2011).

CHAPTER THREE

MATERIALS AND METHODS.

3.0 MATERIALS

3.0.0 PLANT MATERIAL

The plant material used for this study is *Hydrocotyle bonariensis*, common name; large leaf pennywort (Araliaceae; family), harvested from the garden of Prof. O. O Adebawo, Department of Biochemistry, Benjamin S Carson (Snr) School of Medicine Babcock University, Ilishan, Ogun state, Nigeria.

3.0.1 CHEMICAL REAGENTS

All chemical reagents used for this research work are at most of pure analytical grade.

Chloroform, reduced glutathione, dipotassium hydrogen Hydrochloric acid, Methanol, Diethyl ether, Acetic acid, , Thiobarbituric acid, Sucrose, Sodium dodecyl sulphate, Standard malondialdehyde, Potassium chloride, phosphoric acid, n-butanol, Ellman's reagent, Sodium phosphate, Standard glutathione, Tris buffer, Sodium bicarbonate, Potassium dihydrogen phosphate, Sodium dihydrogen phosphate, casein, streptozotocin, distilled water, ethanol, Selenium tablets, Boric acid, Potassium hydroxide (KOH), sodium hydroxide (NaOH), conc. Sulphuric acid(H_2SO_4), chloroform, 0.1M phosphate buffer (pH 7.4), tris buffer (8.0), Kcl (1.15%), Thiobarbituric acid, , phosphate, potassium dihydrogen phosphate, 5'5'-dithiobis(-nitrobenzoic acid) (DTNB), Trichloroacetic acid (TCA), Quercetin, Glacial acetic acid(BDH Chemicals limited), Chloroform(BDH Chemicals limited, England), Potassium dihydrogen phosphate(Surechem products Limited, England),

3.0.2 APPARATUS

Test tubes, test tube racks, hand gloves, nose mask spatula, measuring cylinders (10ml, 25ml, 100ml, 250ml), conical flasks (100ml, 125ml, 250ml), volumetric flasks (100ml, 250ml), Beakers (50ml, 100ml, 250ml), whatman filter paper (1 pack), funnel, pipette sucker, weighing plates, aluminum foil paper, cotton wool, syringes (5ml), Ethylene Diamine tetraacetic acid (EDTA) bottles, plain bottles, labeling tape, glass funnel, centrifuge tubes, stirrer, dropper, cuvette, micro- pipette, Pasteur pipette, Eppendorf tubes, Mechanical Blender, Weighing Balance, pH Meter, UV- Spectrophotometer, Refrigerator, Water Bath, Soxhlet Extractor, Mechanical Blender, Rotary Evaporator, Centrifuge, Weighing Balance, PH Meter, UV- Spectrophotometer, Refrigerator, Water Bath, Refrigerated centrifuge, ice machine

3.1 METHODS

3.1.0 COLLECTION AND IDENTIFICATION OF THE PLANT

Fresh leaves of *Hydrocotyle bonariensis* were collected from the garden of Professor O.O. Adebawo, Department of Biochemistry, Babcock University. The plant leaves were identified by Professor E.B. Esan, a Professor of Plant Breeding and Biotechnology, Department of Basic Sciences, Babcock University Ilishan-Remo, Ogun State.

3.1.1 PREPARATION OF EXTRACTS

The fresh leaves were washed thoroughly with water to remove debris and air-dried at room temperature (26⁰C) for two weeks, after which it was pulverized to powder using a blender.

3.2 PLANT STUDIES

3.2.0 PROXIMATE ANALYSIS

Samples were analyzed chemically according to the official methods of analysis described by the Association of Official Analytical Chemist (A.O.A.C., 18TH EDITION, 2005). All analysis were carried out in triplicates.

3.2.0.0 MOISTURE DETERMINATION

Moisture was determined by the loss in weight that occurs when the sample was dried to a constant weight in the oven. 5g of the sample was weighed into a silica dish previously dried and weighed. The sample was then dried in the oven for 105⁰C for about 4 hours, cooled in a desiccator and weighed. The drying and weighing continued until a constant weight was achieved.

The percentage moisture was calculated using the formula:

$$\% \text{Moisture} = \frac{(\text{weight of sample + dish before drying}) - (\text{weight of sample+ dish after drying})}{\text{Weight of sample taken}} \times 100$$

Weight of sample taken

3.2.0.1 CRUDE PROTEIN DETERMINATION (AOAC OFFICIAL METHOD 988.05)

The crude protein in the sample were determined by the routine semi-micro Kjeldahl, procedure/technique. This consists of three techniques of analysis namely Digestion, Distillation and Titration.

Apparatus: Analytical Balance, Digestion tubes, Digestion Block Heaters, 50ml Burette, 5ml Pipette, 10ml Pipette, 10ml Measuring Cylinder, 100ml Beakers, Fume Cupboard.

Reagents: ConC.H₂SO₄, 0.01NHCL, 40% (W/V) NaOH, 2% Boric Acid Solution, Methyl Red – Bromocresol green mixed indicator, Kjeldahl Catalyst tablet.

Digestion

0.5g of each finely ground dried sample was weighed carefully into the Kjeldahl digestion tubes to ensure that all sample materials got to the bottom of the tubes. To this were added 1 Kjeldahl catalyst tablet and 10ml of ConC. H₂SO₄. These were set in the appropriate hole of the Digestion Block Heaters in a fume cupboard. The digestion was left on for 4 hours, after which a clear colourless solution was left in the tube. The digest was cooled and carefully transferred into 100ml volumetric flask, thoroughly rinsing the digestion tube with distilled water and the flask was made up to mark with distilled water.

Distillation

The distillation was done with Markham Distillation Apparatus which allows volatile substances such as ammonia to be steam distilled with complete collection of the distillate. The apparatus was steamed out for about ten minutes. The steam generator is then removed from the heat source to the entire developing vacuum to remove condensed water. The steam generator is then placed on the heat source (i.e. heating mantle) and each component of the apparatus was fixed up appropriately.

Determination: 5ml portion of the digest above was pipetted into the body of the apparatus via the small funnel aperture. To this was added 5ml of 40% (W/V) NaOH through the same opening with the 5ml pipette.

The mixture was steam-distilled for 2 minutes into a 50ml conical flask containing 10ml of 2% Boric Acid plus mixed indicator solution placed at the receiving tip of the condenser. The Boric Acid plus indicator solution changes colour from red to green showing that all the ammonia liberated have been trapped.

Titration

The green colour solution obtained was then titrated against 0.01N HCL contained in a 50ml Burette. At the end point or equivalent point, the green colour turns to wine colour which indicates that all the Nitrogen trapped as Ammonium Borate ((NH₄)₂BO₃) have been removed as Ammonium chloride (NH₄CL).

The percentage nitrogen in this analysis was calculated using the formula:

$$\% N = \text{Titre value} \times \text{Atomic mass of Nitrogen} \times \text{Normality of HCL used} \times 4$$

$$\text{or } \% N = \text{Titre value} \times \text{Normality/Molarity of HCL used} \times \text{Atomic mass of}$$

$$N \times \text{Volume of flask containing the digest} \times \frac{100}{1}$$

1

Weight of sample digested in milligram x Vol. of digest for steam distillation. The crude protein content is determined by multiplying percentage Nitrogen by a constant factor of 6.25 i.e. % CP = % N x 6.25.

3.2.0.2 CRUDE FAT OR ETHER EXTRACT DETERMINATION (AOAC OFFICIAL METHOD 2003.06)

Apparatus: Soxhlet apparatus and accessories, oven, desiccator and analytical balance.

Reagent: Diethyl ether (40° – 60°C b.pt).

Determination: 1gm of each dried sample was weighed into fat free extraction thimble and pug lightly with cotton wool. The thimble was placed in the extractor and fitted up with reflux condenser and a 250ml soxhlet flask which has been previously dried in the oven, cooled in the desiccator and weighed. The soxhlet flask is then filled to $\frac{3}{4}$ of its volume with petroleum ether (b.pt. 40° – 60°C), and the soxhlet flask. Extractor plus condenser set was placed on the heater. The heater was put on for six hours with constant running water from the tap for condensation of ether vapour. The set is constantly watched for ether leaks and the heat source is adjusted appropriately for the ether to boil gently. The Ether is left to siphon over several times say over at least 10 – 12 times until it is short of siphoning. It is after this is noticed that any ether content of the extractor is carefully drained into the ether stock bottle. The thimble containing sample is then removed and dried on a clock glass on the bench top. The extractor, flask and condenser is replaced and the distillation continues until the flask is practically dry. The flask which now contains the fat or oil is detached, its exterior cleaned and dried to a constant weight in the oven. If the initial weight of dry soxhlet flask is W_0 and the final weight of oven dried flask + oil/fat is W_1 , percentage fat/oil is obtained by the formula:

$$\frac{W_1 - W_0}{\text{Wt. of Sample taken}} \times 100$$

Wt. of Sample taken 1

3.2.0.3 FIBRE DETERMINATION (AOAC 958.06)

Apparatus: Heating mantle, crucibles, furnace, sieve cloth, fibre flask, funnel, analytical weighing balance, a dessicator.

Reagents: 0.255N H₂SO₄, 0.313N NaOH and Acetone.

Determination: 2.0gm of the sample was accurately into the fibre flask and 100ml of 0.255N H₂SO₄ added. The mixture was heated under reflux for 1 hour with the heating mantle. The hot mixture was filtered through a fibre sieve cloth. The filtrate obtained was thrown off and the residue was returned to the fibre flask to which 100ml of (0.313N NaOH) was added and heated under reflux for another 1 hour. The mixture was filtered through a fibre sieve cloth and 10ml of acetone added to dissolve any organic constituent. The residue was washed with about 50ml hot water on the sieve cloth before it was finally transferred into the crucible. The crucible and the residue were oven-dried at 105°C overnight to drive off moisture. The oven-dried crucible containing the residue was cooled in a dessicator and later weighed to obtain the weight W₁. The crucible with weight W₁ was transferred to the muffle furnace for Ashing at 550°C for 4 hours.

The crucible containing white or grey ash (free of carbonaceous material) was cooled in the dessicator and weight to obtain W₂. The difference W₁ – W₂ gives the weight of fibre. The percentage fibre was obtained by the formula:

$$\% \text{ Fibre} = \frac{W_1 - W_2}{\text{wt. of sample}} \times 100$$

3.2.0.4 ASH CONTENT

Ash is the inorganic residue obtained by burning off the organic matter of a material at 400-600⁰C in muffle furnace for 4hrs. 2g of the sample was weighed into a pre-heated crucible. The crucible was placed into the muffle furnace at 400-600⁰C for 4hrs or until whitish-grey ash was obtained. The crucible was then placed in the desiccator and weighed.

The percentage ash was calculated using the following formula:

$$\% \text{Ash} = \frac{\text{weight of crucible+ash} - \text{weight of crucible}}{\text{Weight of sample}}$$

3.3 ANIMAL STUDIES

3.3.0 EXPERIMENTAL ANIMALS

Male albino rats (Wistar strains), weighing between 150-180g was purchased from the animal house; Babcock University, Ilishan-Remo, Ogun State. The animals were acclimatized for 2 weeks. They were given water and rat chow *ad libitum*, and were kept under standard condition of temperature and 12-hour dark/light cycle.

3.3.0.1 HIGH FAT DIET AND LOW DOSE STREPTOZOTOCIN INDUCTION

Male Wistar strain albino rats weighing between 150-180g was used for this study. All rats were provided with commercially available normal pellet diet (NPD) and water *ad libitum* for a period of three weeks before diet manipulation. After acclimatization rats were randomly divide into two groups and fed two dietary regimens: control feed and high fat diet as shown in table 1.

Table 2: Feed composition for normal control and high fat diet fed rats

Component	Normal Control diet (g/kg)	High Fat diet (g/kg)
Carbohydrate (Corn meal)	310	610
Protein (Soyabean cake)	200	200
Saturated fat (Lard)	-	300
Fibre (Rice bran)	90	90
Unsaturated fat (Soya bean oil)	50	50
Mineral mix	20	20
Vitamin mix	20	20
Methionine	2.5	2.5
Lysine	2.5	2.5

After two weeks of dietary manipulation, the rats were intraperitoneally injected with a single dose of streptozotocin at 35mg/kg body weight for the induction of diabetes according to a slight modification of the method described by Srinivasan *et al.*,(2005). Streptozotocin was prepared in 0.1mol/L citrate buffer. Rats that were not injected with streptozotocin were given 1ml of 0.1mol/L citrate buffer. Withdrawal of food 12 hours prior to the assessment of blood glucose was done 72 hours after induction with streptozotocin. Rats with fasting blood glucose \geq 200mg/dL were considered diabetic and were used in the study.

Diabetic rats were divided into three groups and were further placed on different dietary regimen for a period of four weeks while control rats were divided into two groups.

3.3.0.2 EXPERIMENTAL DESIGN

The animal groups are described as follows:

Group I: Normal control rat group which received citrate buffer at pH 4.5, 1ml i.p., and fed on basal diet throughout the period of thirty days.

Group II: Rat group which received citrate buffer at pH 4.5, 1ml i.p., and fed on feed compounded with *H. bonariensis*.

Group III: Diabetic control rat group which fed (i.e. untreated diabetic rats)

Group IV: Diabetic rats fed with rat diet supplemented with 4.3mg quercetin daily

Group V: Diabetic rats fed with feed compounded with *H. bonariensis*.

Table 3: Rat feed for both control and test groups were compounded in the following proportion.

Component	Control (g/kg)	Component	Test (g/kg)
Carbohydrate (Corn meal)	480	Carbohydrate (Corn meal)	480
Fibre (Rice Bran)	100	Fibre (<i>H. bonariensis</i>)	100
Sucrose	100	Sucrose	100
Protein (Casein)	200	Protein (Casein)	200
Unsaturated fat (Soya bean oil)	70	Unsaturated fat (Soya bean oil)	70
Vitamin mix	10	Vitamin mix	10
Mineral mix	35	Mineral mix	35
Methionine	2.5	Methionine	2.5

Lysine	2.5	Lysine	2.5
--------	-----	--------	-----

Cornmeal contains 760g/kg carbohydrate; soyabean cake contains 480g/kg protein; mineral and vitamin premix (10g/kg) contains 3200 i.u. vitamin A, 600 i.u vitamin D₃, 2.8mg vitamin E, 0.6mg vitamin K₃, 0.8mg vitamin B₁, 1mg vitamin B₂, 6mg niacin, 2.2mg pantothenic acid, 0.8mg vitamin B₆, 0.004 mg Vitamin B₁₂, 0.2mg folic acid, 0.1mg biotin H₂, 70mg choline chloride, 0.08mg cobalt, 1.2mg copper, 0.4mg iodine, 8.4mg iron, 16mg manganese, 0.08mg selenium, 12.4mg zinc, 0.5mg zinc antioxidant and lard contains 99% fat.

The feed was pelletized in order to make it appealing to the rats. Approximately 20g feed was given each rat in their compartmentalized cages on a daily basis. Animals from each group were sacrificed weekly with their liver and kidney tissues excised for further analysis prior to being washed thoroughly with 1.15% ice cold KCl. The wet liver and kidney tissues were weighed and homogenized in 0.1M Tris-HCl buffer, pH 7.4 at 4⁰C. The homogenates were centrifuged at 2500rpm for 10 min at 4⁰C using a refrigerated centrifuge. The supernatant was then used for the assay of malondialdehyde (MDA) and reduced glutathione (GSH).

3.4 INDUCTION OF DIABETES MELLITUS

The protocol as designed by Srinivasan *et al.*, 2005 was used for this experiment. A total of 99 rats were randomly divided into five groups. Type 2 Diabetes mellitus was experimentally induced by feeding a high fat diet (HFD) for an initial period of 6 weeks followed by an intraperitoneal injection of 35 mg/kg body weight streptozotocin dissolved in citrate buffer pH 4.5 (Srinivasan *et al.*, 2005). Control rats were given citrate buffer only. Seven days after the injection, rats were screened for serum glucose levels. Rats having serum glucose \geq 200 mg/dl,

after 2 hours of glucose intake, were considered diabetic and selected for further pharmacological studies. The rats were allowed to continue to feed on their respective diets until the end of the study.

3.5 DETERMINATION OF MALONDIALDEHYDE.

The most common method of measuring MDA is based on the reaction with thiobarbituric acid (TBA). The thiobarbituric acid reactive substances (TBARS) assay is the colorimetric method widely used for the detection of lipid peroxidation in biological materials. MDA is formed as a result of lipid peroxidation and reacts with thiobarbituric acid under high temperature (90-100^{0C}) and acidic condition. The reaction yields a pink MDA-TBA adduct.

PRINCIPLE:

Malonyldialdehyde (MDA), an end product of fatty acid peroxidation, can react with TBA to form a colored complex that has maximum absorbance at 532 nm (Stocks and Dormandy, 1971). The colored complex can be extracted into organic solvents such as butanol and measured by fluorometry or spectrophotometry using wavelength 532 nm with an extinction coefficient $\epsilon_{532} = 1.53 \times 10^5 \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ (Nair and Turner, 1984).

REAGENTS

- ❖ 0.67% Thiobarbituric acid (TBA).
- ❖ 20% Trichloroacetic acid.
- ❖ Standard Malondialdehyde.

PREPARATION OF REAGENTS

0.67% Thiobarbituric acid: 0.67g of Thiobarbituric acid was dissolved in 100ml of distilled water. This reagent was prepared fresh just before use.

20% Trichloroacetic acid: 20g of trichloroacetic acid (BDH Chemicals, England) was dissolved in 100 ml of distilled water and kept at 4°C.

PROCEDURE

Liver tissues were homogenized with ice cold 1.5% KCL to make a 10% homogenate. Three milliliters of 1% phosphoric acid and 1ml of 0.6% thiobarbituric acid (TBA) aqueous solution were added to 0.5ml of 10% homogenate. The mixture was heated for 45minutes and after cooling; 4ml of n-butanol was added and mixed. Absorbance of butanol phase was measured at 535nm and 520nm. The difference of the two measurements was used as the MDA value (umol/g tissue). (Mihara and Uchiyama, 1978). **Table 5:** Rat Grouping

GROUP1	GROUP2	GROUP3	GROUP4	GROUP5
Consists of 18 rats and will be fed with normal rat Chow for 5 weeks.	18 diabetic rats and will be fed with the compounded diet that contains the herb (<i>Hydrocotyle bonariensis</i>) for	25 untreated diabetic rats that will be fed with compounded placebo diet.	18 diabetic rats that will be fed with compounded diet that contains 1.5/Kg body weight	20 diabetic rats that will be fed with the compounded diet that contains the

	5 weeks.		quercetin.	herb.
--	----------	--	------------	-------

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS

Data analyses were performed using SPSS software (SPSS 10.0 for Windows, SPSS Inc, Chicago, IL). All data are expressed as mean \pm SEM. Analysis of variance was used to test for differences between the groups. Dunnet's t3 test was used to determine the significance of differences among the mean values at the level of $P \leq 0.05$ (Sokal and Rohlf, 1969).

CHAPTER FOUR

RESULT

4.1 Proximate Analysis Results

The plant (*Hydrocotyle bonariensis*) nutrient % composition is as shown in table 6

Table 6

Nutrient	Percentage %
Ash%	13.0%
Crude Protein%	15.05%
Fat%	5.00%
Crude Fibre%	12.19%
Dry Matter%	92.50%
Moisture%	7.50%
Carbohydrate	54.76%

4.2 EFFECT OF *HYDROCOTYLE BONARIENSIS* ON BODY WEIGHT IN DIABETIC RATS

Table 7 shows that there was significant increased at ($p < 0.05$) in the weight of diabetic rats that had their diets supplemented when compared to the diabetic control. There was

gradual increase in body weight in normal control while the diabetic control continues to lose the weight.

Table 7: EFFECT OF *HYDROCOTYLE BONARIENSIS* ON BODY WEIGHT IN DIABETIC RATS

Treatment	Initial weight (g)	Final weight (g)	% Weight gain
Normal Control	200.22 ± 1.47	256.25 ± 1.55	21.87 ± 5.44
Control + HB	202.25 ± 0.48	243.00 ± 0.41	20.17 ± 17.07
Untreated diabetic rats	190.50 ± 0.65	112.00 ± 0.41	-41.20 ± -36.9
Diabetic rats + quercetin	186.25 ± 0.48	192.00 ± 0.58	3.00 ± 20.83
Diabetic rats + HB	184.00 ± 0.48	189.75 ± 0.58	3.12 ± 20.83

Values expressed in MEAN ± S.E.M (n=4)

Figure 6: A graph showing the effect of *Hydrocotyle bonariensis* on body weight in diabetic rats.

4.3 EFFECT OF *HYDROCOTYLE BONARIENSIS* ON BLOOD GLUCOSE IN DIABETIC RATS

Streptozotocin treatment produced significant increase in blood glucose level ($P < 0.001$) with respect to normal control group. *Hydrocotyle bonariensis* treated diabetic rats did not show significant change in blood glucose level. The changes in blood glucose estimation in all groups of animal were given in Table 8.

Table 8 Fasting blood glucose levels of rat before and after 3 weeks of treatment.

Treatment	Initial (mg/dl)	Final (mg/dl)
Normal Control	92.25 ± 0.47	86.25 ± 0.49
Control + HB	97.00 ± 0.40	91.50 ± 0.29

Untreated diabetic rats	286.50 ± 0.29	314.25 ± 0.46
Diabetic rats + quercetin	317.50 ± 0.29	320.50 ± 0.29
Diabetic rats + HB	301.67 ± 0.33	357.00 ± 18.6

Figure 7: A graph showing the fasting blood glucose levels of rat before and after 3 weeks of treatment.

Table 9: LEVEL OF MALONDIALDEHYDE (LIVER) IN DIABETIC, TREATED AND NON DIABETIC GROUPS.

MALONDIALDEHYDE	umol/g tissue	umol/g tissue	umol/g tissue	umol/g tissue
LIVER	WEEK 1	WEEK 2	WEEK 3	WEEK 4
GROUP				
GROUP I	0.11 ± 0.02	0.22 ± 0.02	2.91 ± 0.01	0.09±0.13
GROUP II	1.58 ± 0.07	0.13 ± 0.01	0.35 ± 0.01	1.00±0.04
GROUP III	2.22 ± 0.01	6.08 ± 0.06	5.032 ± 0.01	6.17±0.01
GROUP IV	1.67 ± 0.06	3.38 ± 0.03	2.00 ± 0.69	1.00±0.54
GROUP V	2.08 ± 0.07	3.70 ± 0.01	1.02 ± 0.01	1.90±0.01

Key

I: Normal Control.

II: Control + HB.

III: Untreated diabetic rats.

IV: Diabetic rats + quercetin.

V: Diabetic rats + HB

Table 10: LEVEL OF MALONDIALDEHYDE (KIDNEY) IN DIABETIC, TREATED AND NON-DIABETIC GROUPS.

MALONDIALDEHYDE	WEEK 1	WEEK 2	WEEK 3	WEEK 4
KIDNEY				
GROUP I	0.01 ± 0.05	0.010 ± 0.05	0.11 ± 0.07	0.12±0.12
GROUP II	1.30 ± 0.10	0.03 ± 0.012	0.03 ± 0.100	1.29±0.01
GROUP III	2.62 ± 0.01	2.30 ± 0.02	2.08 ± 0.01	3.03±0.09
GROUP IV	1.31 ± 0.33	0.24 ± 0.055	0.19 ± 0.00	0.90±0.45
GROUP V	3.13 ± 0.02	3.97 ± 0.02	5.41 ± 0.02	3.03±0.02

Key

I: Normal Control.

II: Control + HB.

III: Untreated diabetic rats.

IV: Diabetic rats + quercetin.

V: Diabetic rats + HB

CHAPTER FIVE

DISCUSSION

There has been considerable interest in the concept that the uncontrolled lipid peroxidation is a key contributing factor in the pathophysiology of type 2 diabetes. Lipid peroxidation eventually is a sequence of the injury caused by reactive oxygen species. Free radical damages can accumulate over time and may thereby contribute to cell injury and development of human diseases. Free radicals have been implicated in the development of several diseases including atherosclerosis, diabetes, hypertension, obesity (Delanty and Dichetr, 1998; Sastre *et al.*, 2002).

In the present study we observed significant increase in the level of lipid peroxidation in Type 2 diabetes as compared to the control group. The prolonged exposure to hyperglycemia also leads to the increased in oxidative stress. The study focuses to estimate the levels of malondialdehyde (MDA), a marker of lipid peroxidation and found that level of MDA were higher in diabetics compared to controls. Similar results were reported by Nishio *et al*(1998), Gallow *et al* (1993), Ayden (2001) and Seghrolchhi *et al* (2002) in type 2 DM patients. Diabetes is a risk factor for atherosclerosis which is progressive and associated with enhanced oxidative stress.

Hyperglycemia can induce oxidative stress by several different mechanisms. Autoxidation of glucose and the non-enzymatic glycation of proteins generate superoxide ($O_2^{\cdot-}$) (Baynes, 1991). Chatterjee SN stated that the permeability of the membrane has also been found to be increased in parallel with the lipid peroxidation indicating that the interior of the membrane undergoes alterations (Chatterjee, 1998). Wolff SP *et al* stated that free radicals and oxidative stress may act as a common pathway to diabetes itself as well as to its later complications and found significantly higher MDA levels in diabetic than healthy individuals, matching the study results. Higher levels of lipid peroxidation were observed in diabetic subject with vascular complication

which may be due to the increased activity of the free radical formation. Free radical interacts in arachidonic acid metabolism forming a toxic endoperoxidase. The lipid peroxide thus formed stimulates the synthesis of cyclooxygenase, prostaglandin and thromboxane which in turn causes increased platelets aggregation leading to vascular complications (Suryawanshi *et al.*, 2006). Palanduz S, Ademoglu E *et al* reported that some complications of diabetes mellitus are associated with increased activity of free radicals and accumulation of lipid peroxidation products. The organism susceptibility to free radical stress and peroxidative damage depends upon the balance between the free radical load and the adequacy of antioxidant defenses.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

An imbalance between oxidants and antioxidants is seen in diabetes mellitus which is the basis cause for further complication. Present study showed significantly elevated levels of lipid peroxidation product malondialdehyde (MDA) in rodents at risk of oxidative damages to the cell membrane due to oxidative stress further augmented by the chemical diabetogen streptozotocin. The increase in lipid peroxide is due to the increased activity of the free radical formation and decreased activity of the exogenous antioxidants. A deficiency of the enzymatic and Non-enzymatic activities of systemic antioxidant has been related to higher concentration of lipid peroxide. There is imbalance between production and scavenging free radical produced due to lack of antioxidant system or ineffective antioxidant system. The estimation of lipid peroxidation along in diabetes mellitus is very useful as it may serve as a useful monitor to judge the prognosis of the patients. The detection of risk factors in the early stage of the disease will help the patient to improve and reduce the morbidity rate. Thus according to these reports it may be proposed that along with clinical examination, estimation of oxidative stress may serve as supportive additional biochemical markers for early diagnosis and therapeutic intervention.

Therapy of supplementation of the leaves of *Hydrocotyle bonanriensis* may prevent or reduce the risk of diabetic complications in diabetes mellitus.

REFERENCES

- Abdel-Zaher AO, Salim SY, Assaf MH, Abdel-Hady RH.2005. Antidiabetic activity and toxicity of *Zizyphus spina-chnsti* leaves. *Journal of Ethnopharmacology*. **101**: 129-138.
- Ahmed RG.2005. The physiological and biochemical effects of diabetes on the balance between oxidative stress and antioxidant defense system. *Medical Journal of the Islamic World academy of Sciences*. **15**(1):31-42.
- Alexander, G.C. 2008 National trends in treatment of type 2 diabetes mellitus, 1994-2007. *Jama Internal Medicine*. **168**(19): 2088-94.
- American Diabetes Association. "Insulin Basics" Retrieved 24 March, 2014
- American Diabetes Association. 2004. Diagnosis and classification of diabetes mellitus. *Diabetes care*.**27**(supplement 1): S5-S10.
- [American Diabetes Association](#). 2010. Diabetes Care" Retrieved on February, 2015.
- American Diabetes Association. 2011. Diagnosis and classification of diabetes mellitus: position statement. *Diabetes Care*.**28** (supplement 1):S37-S4
- American Diabetes, Association. 2013. ["Economic costs of diabetes in the U.S. in 2012."](#). *Diabetes Care*. **36** (4): 1033–46.
- Anderson ME. 1998. Glutathione: an overview of biosynthesis and modulation. *Chemico-Biological Interactions*. **111**–2:1–14.
- Asahina, T., Kashiwagi, A., Nishio, Y.1995. Impaired activation of glucose oxidation and NADPH supply in human endothelial cells exposed to H₂O₂ in high-glucose medium. *Diabetes*. **44**: 520–526.

- Ashokkumar D, Mazumder UK, Gupta M, Senthilkumar GP, Selvan VT. 2005. Evaluation of Antioxidant and Free Radical Scavenging Activities of *Oxystelma esculentum* in various in vitro Models. *Journal of Computer Integrated Medicine*. **5**(1): 1-6.
- Balamurugan, A.N., Miyamoto, M., Wang, W., Inoue, K., Tabata, Y. 2003. Streptozotocin (STZ) used to induce diabetes in animal models. *Journal of Ethnopharmacology*. **26**: 102-103.
- Bartosikova, L., Nieces, J., Succhy, V., Kubinov, R., Vesa-la, D., Benes, L. 2003. Monitoring of antioxidative effect of *morine* in alloxan-induced diabetes mellitus in the laboratory rat. *Acta Veterinaria Scandinavica*. **72**:191-200.
- Basaram PH, Kalansooriya A, Holbrook I, Haddad F, Jennings PE. 1996. The relationship between chronic glycaemic control and oxidative stress in type 2 diabetes mellitus. *British Journal of Biomedical Science*. **65**:71–74
- Basaran A, Yu TW, Plewa MJ, Anderson D. 1996. An investigation of some Turkish herbal medicines in *Salmonella typhimurium* and the Comet assay in human lymphocytes, *Teratogenesis Carcinogenesis and Mutagenesis*. **16**:125–138.
- Baynes, J.W. and Thorpe S.R. 1996. Role of oxidative stress in diabetic complications: a new perspective on an old paradigm. *Diabetes*. **48**: 1–9.
- Bent S, Ko R. 2004. Commonly used herbal medicines in the United States: A review, *American Journal of Medicine*. **16**:78–485.
- Berdainer, C.D.2003. Vitamin A needs in diabetes mellitus. *Sight Life Newsletter*.**1**: 3–17.
- Bláha I, Kopp R, Šimková K, Mareš J. 2004: Oxidative stress biomarkers are modulated in silver carp (*Hypophthalmichthys molitrix* Val.) exposed to microcystin-producing cyanobacterial water bloom. *Universitas veterinaria et pharmaceutica* **73**: 477-482.

- Braca, A, Sortino, C, Politi, M, Morelli, I, Mendez, J.2002. Antioxidant activity of flavonoids from *Licania licaniaeflora*. *Journal of Ethnopharmacology*: **79**: 379-381.
- Brown RK, ScBurney A, Lunec J, Kelly FJ.1995. Oxidative damage to DNA in patients with cystic fibrosis.*Free Radical Biology and Medicine*: **234**: 137–46.
- Brown RK, Wyatt H, Price JF, Kelly FJ.1996. Pulmonary dysfunction in cystic fibrosis is associated with oxidative stress. *European Respiratory Journal* **9**:334–9.
- Brownlee, M. 2001. Biochemistry and molecular cell biology of diabetic complications. *Nature*. 414: 813–820.
- Brownlee, M. 2001. Biochemistry and molecular cell biology of diabetic complications. *Nature*. **414** (6865), 813-820.
- Cai YZ, Sun M, Corke H. 2003. Antioxidant activity of betalains from plants of the Amaranthaceae. *Journal of Agricultural Food Chemistry*. **51**(8): 2288-2294.
- Ceriello, A. 2006. Oxidative stress and diabetes-associated complications. *Endocrinology Practice*. **12**(1), 60-62.
- Charles.H.B. 1962.”some thoughts on the etiology of human diabetes” *Canadian Journal Of Diabetes*. **87**:731-734.
- Chebil, L, Humeau, C, Falcimaigne, A, Engasser, J, Ghoul, M. 2006. Enzymatic acylation of flavonoids. *Process Biochemistry*. **41**: 2237-2251.
- Chou, T. Y., Hart, G. W. and Dang, C. V.1995.c-Myc is glycosylated at threonine 58, a known phosphorylation site and a mutational hot spot in lymphomas *Journal of Biological Chemistry*. **270**: 18961–18965

- Cook, NC, Samman, S. 1996. Flavonoids: Chemistry, metabolism, cardioprotective effects and dietary sources. *Nutritional Biochemistry*. **7**: 66-76.
- Cordell G. 2002. Natural products in drug discovery creating a new vision, *Phytochemistry Reviews*: **1**: 261-273.
- Creager, M. A., Luscher, T. F., Cosentino, F., and Beckman, J. A. 2003. Diabetes and vascular disease: pathophysiology, clinical consequences, and medical therapy: part I. *Circulation* **108** :1527–1532.
- Cuerda, C., Luengo, L. M., Valero, Vidal. A., Burgos, R., Calvo, F. L. 2011. Antioxidants and diabetes mellitus: review of the evidence). *Nutricion Hospitalaria*. **26**(1), 68-78.
- Cushnie, TPT, Lamb, AJ. 2005. Antimicrobial activity of flavonoids. *International Journal of Antimicrobial Agents*. **26**: 343-356.
- D'Agostino RB, Russell MW, Huse DM. 2000. Primary and subsequent coronary risk appraisal: new results from the Framingham Study *American Heart Journal*. **139**:272-281.
- David G. Gardner, Dolores .2011. *Greenspan's basic & clinical endocrinology* (9th ed.) New York. Chapter 17". McGraw-Hill Medical. pp 124-168.
- Day, T.A., Cunningham, C.C. and Bailey, S.M. 2002. *Archives of Biochemistry and Biophysics*. **405**: 65–72.
- De Sa Ferreira ICF, Vargas VM. 1999. Mutagenicity of medicinal plant extracts in *Salmonella*/microsome assay, *Phytotherapy Research*. **13**:397–400.
- Decio, E. L., Sandler, S., Welsh, N. and Hellerstrom, C. 1988. Preferential reduction of insulin production in mouse pancreatic islets maintained in culture after streptozotocin exposure. *Endocrinology*. **122**: 1242–1249.
- DeFronzo RA, Ferrannini E. 1991. Insulin resistance: a multifaceted syndrome responsible for NIDDM, obesity, hypertension, dyslipidemia, and atherosclerotic cardiovascular disease. *Diabetes Care*. **14**:

173–194.

- Demma J, Engidawork E, Hellman B. 2009. Potential genotoxicity of plant extracts used in Ethiopian traditional medicine, *Journal of Ethnopharmacology*. **122**: 136–142.
- Dias as, porawski m, alonso m, marroni n, collado ps, gonzález-gallego j.2005. Quercetin decreases oxidative stress, NF-B activation, and iNOS overexpression in liver of streptozotocin induced diabetic rats. *Journal of Nutrition*. **135**: 2299-2304.
- Diczfalusy U, Falardeau P, Hammarstrom S.1977. Conversion of prostaglandin endoperoxides to C17-hydroxy acids catalyzed by human platelet thromboxane synthase. *FEBS Letters*. **84**:271-274.
- Dineshkumar, H., Aubert, R. E., & Herman, W. H. 2010. Global burden of diabetes, 1995-2025: prevalence, numerical estimates, and projections. *Diabetes Care*, 21(9).1414-1431.
- Dondona, P., Thusu, K., Snyder, B. 1996. Oxidative damage to DNA in diabetes mellitus. *Lancet*. **347**: 444–445.
- Dyer, D.G., Dunn, J.A., Thorpe, S.R. 1993. Accumulation of Maillard reaction products in skin collagen in diabetes and aging. *Journal of Clinical Investigation*. **91**: 2463–2469.
- Edeoga HO, Okwu OE, Mbaebie BO. 2005. Phytochemical constituents of some Nigerian medicinal plants, *African Journal of Biotechnology*. **1**:685-688.
- Edeoga HO, Okwu OE, Mbaebie BO. 2005. Phytochemical constituents of some Nigerian medicinal plants, *African Journal of Biotechnology*. **1**:685-688.
- Eizirik, D. L., Sandier, S., Ahnstrom, G. and Welsh, M.1991. Exposure of pancreatic islets to different alkylating agents decreases mitochondrial DNA content, but only streptozotocin induces long-lasting

functional impairment of β -cells. *Journal of Pharmacological Biochemistry*. **42**: 2275–2282

Evans JP.1992. The Effect of Local Resource Availability and Clonal Integration on Ramet Functional Morphology in *Hydrocotyle bonariensis*, *Oecologia*, **89** (2): 265-27.

Fernandez, SP, Wasowski, C, Loscalzo, LM, Granger, RE, Johnston, GAR, Paladini, AC, Marder, M.2006. Central nervous system depressant action of flavonoid glycosides. *European Journal of Pharmacology* **539**: 168-176.

Ferreira, J, F, S, Luthria, D,L, Sasaki, T, Heyerick, A.2010. Flavonoids from *Artemisia annua* as antioxidants and their potential synergism with Artemisinin against malaria and cancer. *Molecules*. **15**: 3135-3170.

Fisher C, Speth V, Fleig-Eberenz S, Neuhaus G.1997. induction of zygotic polyembryos in wheat influence of auxin polar transport. *Plant cell*. **9** (10): 1767-80.

Fisher, A. B., Zhang, Q. Â. Â., Geoffrey, J. L., & Steven, D.S. 2006. Nadph and nadph oxidase. *Encyclopedia of Respiratory Medicine*. Oxford, academic Press. 77.

Fu, M.X., Requena, J.R., Jenkins, A.J. 1996. The advanced glycation end product, Nepsilon-(carboxymethyl) lysine, is a product of both lipid peroxidation and glycoxidation reactions. *Journal of Biological Chemistry*. **271**: 9982–9986.

Ge´rard-Monnier D, Erdelmeier I, Re´gnard K, Moze-Henry N, Yadan JC, Chaudie`re J Ge´rard-.1997.Reactions of N-Methyl-2-phenylindole with Malondialdehyde and 4-Hydroxyalkenals. *Analytical Applications to a Colorimetric Assay of Lipid Peroxidation, Chemical Research in Toxicology* **11**:1176-1183.

Giacco, F., Brownlee, M.2005.Oxidative stress and diabetic complications. *Circulation Research*. **107(9)**, 1058-1070.

- Gill, G., Pascal, E., Tseng, Z. H. and Tjian, R.1994. A glutamine-rich hydrophobic patch in transcriptional factor Sp1 contacts the dTAF2110 component of the *Drosophila* TF2D complex and mediates transcriptional activation. *Proceedings of the National academy of Sciences of the United States of America*. **91**, 192–196.
- Giugliano, D., Ceriello, A., and Paolisso, G.1996. Oxidative stress and diabetic vascular complications. *Diabetes Care*. **19**:257–267.
- Giugliano, D., Paolisso, G. and Ceriello, A.1996. Oxidative stress and diabetic vascular complications. *Diabetes Care*. **19**: 257–267.
- Golden, P., Baird, L., Malaisse, W. J., Malaisse-Lagae, F. and Walker, M. M.1976. Effect of 1-methyl-1-nitrosourea and streptozotocin on glucose-induced insulin secretion by isolated islets of Langerhans. *Diabetologia* .**12**: 207–209.
- Goldwasser, I.2000. Insulin-like effects of vanadium: basic and clinical implications. *Journal of Inorganic Biochemistry* .**80**: 21–25, 2000.
- Halliwell B, Gutteridge JMC.1999. Free radicals in biology and medicine 3rd ed. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Han, I.O. and Kudlow, J. E.1997. Reduced O-glycosylation of Sp1 is associated with increased proteasome susceptibility. *Molecular and Cell Biology of Human Diseases Series*. **17**: 2550–2558
- Hanover, J. A., Lai, Z., Le, G., Lubas, W. A. and Sato, S. M.1999. Elevated O-linked N-acetylglucosamine metabolism in pancreatic beta-cells. *Archives of Biochemistry and Biophysics* **367**: 51–60.

- Hart, G. W. 1997. Dynamic O-GlcNAcylation of nuclear and cytoskeletal proteins. *Annual Review of Biochemistry*. **66**:315–335
- Havsteen, BH.2002. The biochemistry and medical significance of the flavonoids. *Pharmacology and Therapeutics*. **96**: 67-202.
- Heim, KE, Tagliaferro, AR, Bobliya, DJ. 2002. Flavonoids antioxidants: Chemistry, metabolism and structure activity relationships. *The Journal of Nutritional Biochemistry* . **13**: 572-584.
- Herr, R. R., Jahnke, J. K. and Argoudelis, A. D. 1967. The structure of streptozotocin. *American Journal of Chemistry Society*. **89**: 4808–4809.
- Hollman, PCH, Katan, MB.1999. Dietary Flavonoids: Intake, Health Effects and Bioavailability. *Food and Chemical Toxicology*: **37**: 937-942.
- Hotta, H, Nagano, S, Ueda, M, Tsujino, Y, Koyama, J, Osakai, T.2002. Higher radical scavenging activity of polyphenolic antioxidants ascribed to chemical reactions following oxidation. *Biochimica et Biophysica Acta*: **1572**: 123-132.
- Hyun, D. H., Lee, M., Hattori, N., Kubo, S., Mizuno, Y., Halliwell, B. 2002. Effect of wild-type or mutant Parkin on oxidative damage, nitric oxide, antioxidant defenses, and the proteasome. *Journal of Biological Chemistry*. **277**:28572–28577.
- International Diabetes Federation (INTERNATIONAL DIABETES FEDERATION).2014. Accessed 29 February, 2015.
- International Diabetes Federation. 2014. *INTERNATIONAL DIABETES FEDERATION Diabetes Atlas*. 4th edition. Brussels: International Diabetes Federation.

- Jackson, S. P. and Tjian, R. 1988. O-Glycosylation of eukaryotic transcription factors: implications for mechanisms of transcriptional regulation. *Cell* .55:125–133
- Janero DR. 1990. Malondialdehyde and thiobarbituric acid-reactivity as diagnostic indices of lipid peroxidation and peroxidative tissue injury. *Free Radical Biology and Medicine*. 9:515-540
- Jiang, M. S. and Hart, G. W. 1997. A sub-population of estrogen receptors are modified by O-linked N-acetylglucosamine. *Journal of Biological Chemistry* .272:2421–2428
- Johansen, J. S., Harris, A. K., Rychly, D. J., & Ergul, A. 2005. Oxidative stress and the use of antioxidants in diabetes: linking basic science to clinical practice. *Cardiovascular Diabetology*. 4(1), 5.
- Jung, WY, Park, SJ, Park, DH, Kim, JM, Kim, DH, Ryu, JH. 2010. Quercetin impairs learning and memory in normal mice via suppression of hippocampal phosphorylated cyclic AMP response element binding protein expression. *Toxicological letters*. 197: 97-105.
- Kadonaga, J. T., Courey, A. J., Ladika, J. and Tjian, R. 1988. distinct regions of Sp1 modulate DNA binding and transcriptional activation. *Science*. 242: 1566–1570
- Kashiwagi, A., Asahina, T., Takagi, Y. 1994. Abnormal glutathione metabolism and increased cytotoxicity caused by H₂O₂ in human umbilical vein endothelial cells cultured in high glucose medium. *Diabetologia*. 37: 264–269.
- Kim E. Barrett. 2012. *Ganong's review of medical physiology*. (24th ed.). New York: McGraw-Hill Medical.
- Kitts DD, Yuan YV, Wijewickreme AN, Hu C. 2000. Antioxidant properties of a North American ginseng extract. *Molecular and Cellular Biochemistry* . 20(3):1-10.

- Kornfeld, R. 1967. Studies on L-glutamine D-fructose 6-phosphate amidotransferase: feedback inhibition by uridine diphosphate-N-acetylglucosamine. *Journal of Biological Chemistry*. **242**:3135–3141.
- Kreppel, L. K., Blomberg, M. A. and Hart, G. W. 1997. Dynamic glycosylation of nuclear and cytosolic proteins. Cloning and characterization of a unique O-GlcNAc transferase with multiple tetratricopeptide repeats. *Journal of Biological Chemistry*. **272**:9308–9315.
- Kroncke, K. D., Fehsel, K., Sommer, A., Rodriguez, M. L. and Kolb-Bachofen, V. 1995. Nitric oxide generation during cellular metabolization of the diabetogenic N-methyl-N-nitroso-urea streptozotocin contributes to islet cell DNA damage. *Biological Chemistry*. **376**: 179–185
- Krssak, M. 1999. Intramyocellular lipid concentrations are correlated with insulin sensitivity in humans: a ¹H NMR spectroscopy study. *Diabetologia*. **42**: 113–116.
- LeDoux, S. P., Woodley, S. E., Patton, N. J. and Wilson, G. L. 1986. Mechanisms of nitrosourea-induced β -cell damage. *Diabetes*. **35**: 866–872.
- Lefevre G, Bonneau C, Rahma S, Chanu B, Brault D, Couderc R, Etienne J. 1996. Determination of plasma protein-bound malondialdehyde by derivative spectrophotometry. *European Journal of Clinical Chemistry and Clinical Biochemistry*. **34**:631-636.
- Li, F, Li, Q, Gao, D, Peng, Y. 2009. The optimal extraction parameters and anti-diabetic activity of flavonoids from *Ipomoea batatas* leaf. *African Journal of Traditional, Complementary and Alternative Medicines*. **6**: 195-202.
- Liu, K., Paterson, A. J., Chin, E. and Kudlow, J. E. (2000) Glucose stimulates protein modification by O-linked GlcNAc in pancreatic β -cells: linkage of O-linked GlcNAc to β -cell death. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America*. **97**, 2820–2825.

- Lkouri N, Dixon LJ, Feldstein AE. Lipotoxicity in nonalcoholic fatty liver disease. 2009. Not all lipids are created equal. *Expert Review on Gastroenterology and Hepatology*. **3**:445-451.
- Lubas, W. A., Frank, D. W., Krause, M. and Hanover, J. A.1997. O-Linked GlcNAc transferase is a conserved nucleocytoplasmic protein containing tetratricopeptide repeats. *Journal of Biological Chemistry*.**272**:9316–9324.
- Lucke-Wold BP, Turner RC, Lucke-Wold AN, Rosen CL, Huber JD. 2012. Age and the metabolic syndrome as risk factors for ischemic stroke: improving preclinical models of ischemic stroke. *Yale Journal of Biology and Medicine* .**85**: 523-539.
- Macedo, C.S., Capelletti, S.M., Mercadante, M.C.S., Padovani, C.R., Spadella C.T. 2005. Experimental model of induction of diabetes mellitus in rats. *Plastic surgery, laboratory of plastic surgery*. Sao Paulo –Paulista School of Medicine. Pp 2-5.
- Maritim, A. C., Sanders, R. A., & Watkins, J. B.2003. Diabetes, oxidative stress, and antioxidants: A review. *Journal of Biochemical and Molecular Toxicology*, **17**(1):24.
- Marnette LJ. 1999. Generation of mutagens during arachidonic acid metabolism. *Cancer Metastasis Review*.13:303-308.
- Masiello P.2006. Animal models of type11 diabetes with reduced pancreatic β -cell mass. *The international Journal of Biochemistry and Cell Biology*. 38:873-893.
- Masoumian M, Arbakariya A, Syahida A, Maziah M. 2011. Flavonoids production in *Hydrocotyle bonariensis* callus tissues, *Journal of Medicinal Plants Research*.5 (9):1564-1574.
- Mc Call MR, Frei B.1999. Can antioxidant vitamins maternally reduce oxidative damage in humans? *Journal of Free Radicals in Biology and Medicine*. **26**: 1034-1053.

- McGarry, J. D. 1992. What if Minkowski had been ageusic? An alternative angle on diabetes. *Science* **258**:766–770.
- McKnight, G. U., Mudd, S. L., Mathewes, S. L., Traxinger, R. R., Marshall, S., Sheppard, P. O. and O'Hara, P. J. 1992. Molecular cloning, CDNA sequence, and bacterial expression of human glutamine fructose-6-phosphate amidotransferase. *Journal of Biological Chemistry*. **267**, 25208–25212.
- Mealey BL, Ocampo GL. 2000. Diabetes mellitus. *Periodontology 2000* (in press).
- Middleton, EJR Kandaswami, C, Theoharides, TC. 2000. The Effects of Plant Flavonoids on Mammalian cells: Implications for inflammation, heart disease, and cancer. *Pharmacological Reviews*. **52**: 673-751.
- Mohanty, P., Hamouda, W., Garg, R., Aljada, A., Ghanim, H., and Dandona, P. 2000. Glucose challenge stimulates reactive oxygen species (ROS) generation by leucocytes. *Journal of Clinical Endocrinology and Metabolism*. **85**: 2970–2973.
- Mossman, B. T., Ireland, C. M., Filipak, M., LeDoux, S. and Wilson, G. L. 1986. Comparative interactions of streptozotocin and chlorozotocin with DNA of insulin secreting cell line. *Diabetologia*. **29**: 186–191.
- Mshelia, D.S., Habu, S.A., Buba, A.A. 2005. Factors militating against diabetic dietary therapy in North-Eastern Nigeria. *Journal of Diabetes International*, **3**, 14–16.
- Mullarkey, C.J., Edelstein, D. and Brownlee, M. 1990. Free radical generation by early glycation products: a mechanism for accelerated atherogenesis in diabetes. *Biochemical and Biophysical Research Communications*. **173**: 932–939.
- Mullineaux P, Creissen GP. 1997. Glutathione reductase: regulation and role in oxidative stress. Oxidative stress and the molecular biology of antioxidant defenses. Cold Spring Harbor Laboratory Press.
- Murray, MT. 1998. Quercetin: Nature's antihistamine. *Better Nutrition*.

- Nair V, Turner GA. 1984. The thiobarbituric acid test for lipid peroxidation: structure of the adduct with malondialdehyde. *Lipids*. 19:804-805.
- Narayan MS, Venkataraman LV. 2002. Effect of sugar and nitrogen on the production of anthocyanin in carrot (*Daucus carita*) cells. *Journal of Food Science*. **67**: 84-86.
- Narayana, KR, Reddy, SR, Chaluvadi, MR, Krishna, DR. 2001. Bioflavonoids classification, pharmacological, biochemical effects and therapeutic potential. *Indian Journal of Pharmacology*: **33**: 2-16.
- Nathan DM, Cleary PA, Backlund JY, Genuth SM, Lachin JM, Orchard TJ, Raskin P, Zinman B. 2005. "Intensive diabetes treatment and cardiovascular disease in patients with type 1 diabetes". *The New England Journal of Medicine* .**353 (25)**: 2643–53.
- Naviaux, R. K. 2012. Oxidative Shielding or Oxidative Stress? *Journal of Pharmacology Expert Therapeutics*.
- Nielsen F, Mikkelsen BB, Nielsen JB, Andersen HR, Grandjean P. 1997. Plasma malondialdehyde as biomarker for oxidative stress: reference interval and effects of life-style factors. *Clinical Chemistry*. **43(7)**:1209- 14.
- Nishikawa, T., Edelstein, D., Du X.L. 2000. Normalizing mitochondrial superoxide production blocks three pathways of hyperglycemic damage. *Nature*. **404**: 787–790.
- Nishio, Y., Kashiwagi, A., Taki, H. 1998. Altered activities of transcription factors and their related gene expression in cardiac tissues of diabetic rats. *Diabetes*. **47**: 1318–1325.
- Ntui, I., Udoh, A.E., Kaiso-Umo, S.E., Essien, O., Egbe, E.R. 2006. The pattern of dietary habits and glycemic control of diabetics in eastern Nigeria. *Pakistan Journal of Nutrition*, 5(1),43-54.

- Pal, RS, Ariharasivakumar, G, Girhepunjhe, K, Upadhay, A.2009. In-vitro antioxidative activity of phenolic and flavonoids compounds extracted from seeds of *Abrus precatorius*. *International Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences*.**1**: 136-140.
- Palanduz S, Ademoglu E, Gokkusu C, Tamer S. 2001. *Research Communication in Molecular pathology and pharmacology*. **109 (56)**: 309-318.
- Patra, JC, Chua, BH. 2010. Artificial neural network-based drug design for diabetes mellitus using flavonoids. *Journal of Computational Chemistry*: **32**: 555- 567.
- Peterson, J, Dwyer, MSJ, RD, DSc.1998. Flavonoids: Dietary occurrence and biochemical activity. *Nutrition Research*. **18**: 1995-2018.
- Plastaras JP, Guengerich FP, Nebert DW, Marnett LJ. 2000. Xenobiotic-metabolizing cytochromes P450 convert prostaglandin endoperoxide to hydroxyheptadecatrienoic acid and the mutagen, malondialdehyde. *Journal of Biological Chemistry*. **275**:11784-11790.
- Pratico, D., Basili, S., Vieri, M., Cordova, C., Violi, F., and Fitzgerald, G. A. 1998. Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease is associated with an increase in urinary levels of isoprostane F_{2α}-2I, an index of oxidant stress. *American Journal of Respiratory and Critical Care Medicine*. **158**:1709–1714.
- Pratico, D.1999. F(2)-isoprostanes: sensitive and specific non-invasive indices of lipid peroxidation in vivo. *Atherosclerosis*. **147**:1–10.
- Rains, J. L.,Jain, S. K. 2011. Oxidative stress, insulin signaling, and diabetes. *Free Radical Biology and Medicine*. **50(5)**: 567-575.
- Ramos, S. 2007. Effects of dietary flavonoids on apoptic pathways related to cancer chemoprevention. *Journal of Nutritional Biochemistry*. **18**: 427- 442.

- Reason, A. J., Morris, M. L., Panico, M., Marais, R., Treisman, R. H., Haltiwanger, R. S., Hart, G. W., Kelly, W. G. and Dell, A.1992. Localization of O-GlcNAc modification on the serum response transcription factor. *Journal of Biological Chemistry*. **267**: 16911–16921
- Rees, D.A., Alcolado, J.C.2005. Animal models of diabetes mellitus. *Diabetic Medicine*. **22**:359-370.
- Rice-Evans CA, Miller NJ, Bolwell PG, Bramley PM, Pridham JB.1995. The relative activities of Plant-derived polyphenolic flavonoid. *Free Radical Research*. **22**: 375-383.
- Rijke, ED, Out, P, Niessen, WMA, Ariese, F, Goojer, C, Brinkman, UAT. 2006. Analytical separation and detection methods for flavonoids. *Journal of Chromatography* . **1112**: 31-63.
- Robert K. Murray .2012. *Harper's illustrated biochemistry* (29th ed.). New York: McGraw-Hill Medical. Pp 60-74.
- Roberts, L. J. and Morrow, J. D. 2000. Measurement of F(2)-isoprostanes as an index of oxidative stress in vivo. *Free Radical Biology and Medicine*. **28**: 505–513.
- Rodrigues, B., Poucheret, P., Betell, M.L., Mc Neill, J.N.1999. Streptozotocin – Induced Diabetes: Induction, Mechanism(s), and Dose Dependency, in: McNeill’s J.H. (Ed.), *Experimental Models of Diabetes*. CRC Press LLC, USA, pp. 3–17.
- Romero-Jimenez M, Campos-Sanchez J, Allana M, MunozSerrano A, Alonso-Moraga A.2005. Genotoxicity and antigenotoxicity of some traditional medicinal herbs, *Mutation Research*. **585**:147–155.
- Roos, M. D., Su, K., Baker, J. R. and Kudlow, J. E.1997. O-Glycosylation of an Sp1-derived peptide blocks known Sp1 protein interactions. *Molecular and Cell Biology of Human Diseases Series*. **17**: 6472–6480.

- Roos, M. D., Wen, X., Kaihong, S., Clark, J. A., Xiaoyong, Y., Chin, E., Paterson, A. J. and Kudlow, J. E. 1998. Streptozotocin, an analog of N-acetylglucosamine, blocks the removal of O-GlcNAc from intracellular proteins. *Proceedings of the Association of American Physicians* .**110**:1–11.
- Rosen, P., Du, X., and Tschope, D. 1998. Role of oxygen derived radicals for vascular dysfunction in the diabetic heart: prevention by alphatocopherol. *Molecular and Cellular Biochemistry*. **188**:103–111.
- Ruderman, N. B., Saha, A. K., Vavvas, D. & Witters, L. A. 1999. Malonyl-CoA, fuel sensing, and insulin resistance. *American Journal of Physiology*. **276**: E1–E18.
- Rydgren T., Vaarala O., Sandler S. 2007. Simvastatin protects against multiple low dose streptozotocin induced type 1 diabetes in CD-1 mice and recurrence of the disease in nonobese diabetic mice. *Journal of Pharmacology and Expert Therapeutics*. **323**: 180-185.
- Sahu, SC, Gray, GC.1996. Pro-oxidant activity of flavonoids: effect on glutathione and glutathione-Transferase in isolated rat liver nuclei. *Cancer letters*. **104**: 193-196
- Sala A, Recio MD, Giner RM, Manez S, Tournier H, Schinella G, Rios JL. 2002 Antinflammatory and antioxidant properties of Helichrysum italicum. *journal of Pharmacy and Pharmacology*. **54(3)**: 365-371.
- Salucci, M, Stivala, LA, Maiani, G, Vannini, V.2002. Flavonoids uptake and their effect on cell cycle of human colon adenocarcinoma cells. *British Journal of Cancer*. **86**: 1645-1651.
- Sayeski, P. P., Paterson, A. J. and Kudlow, J. E.1994. The murine glutamine : fructose-6-phosphate amidotransferase-encoding cDNA sequence. *Gene*. **140**: 289–290.
- Sayeski, P. P., Wang, D., Su, K., Han, I.-O. and Kudlow, J. E.1997. Cloning and partial characterization of the mouse glutamine : fructose-6-phosphate amidotransferase (GFAT) gene promoter. *Nucleic Acids Research*. **25**:1458–1466.

- Selvin E, Steffes MW, Zhu H, Matsushita K, Wagenknecht L, Pankow J, Coresh J, Brancati FL 2010. ["Glycated hemoglobin, diabetes, and cardiovascular risk in nondiabetic adults"](#). *New England Journal of Medicine*. **362 (9)**: 800–11.
- Sevilla CL, Mahle NH, Eliezer N, Uzieblo A, O'Hara SM, Nokubo M, Miller R, Rouzer CA, Marnett LJ. 1997. Development of monoclonal antibodies to the malondialdehyde deoxyguanosine adduct, pyrimidopurinone. *Chemical Research in Toxicology*. **10**:172-180.
- Sheetz, M. J. and King, G. L. 2002. Molecular understanding of hyperglycemia's adverse effects for diabetic complications. *JAMA: Journal of the American medicine*. **288**: 2579–2588.
- Sheikh-Ali, M., Chehade, J. M., & Mooradian, A. D. 2011. The antioxidant paradox in diabetes mellitus. *American Journal of Therapeutics*. **18(3)**:266-278.
- Sheikh-Ali, M., Chehade, J. M., & Mooradian, A. D. 2011. The antioxidant paradox in diabetes mellitus. *American Journal of Therapeutics*, 18(3), 266-278.
- Shoback, edited by David G. Gardner, Dolores .2011. *Greenspan's basic & clinical endocrinology* (9th ed.). New York: McGraw-Hill Medical.Pp 65-98
- Skerget, M, Kotnik, P, hadolin, M, Hras, AR, Simonic, M, Knez, Z.2005. Phenols, proanthocyanidins, flavones and flavonols in some plant materials and their antioxidant activities. *Food Chemistry*. **89**: 191-198.
- Slade, D, Ferreira, D, Marais, JPJ.2005. Circular dichroism, a powerful tool for the assessment of absolute configuration of flavonoids. *Phytochemistry* .**66**; 2177-2215.
- Sohni Y, Davis C, Champs A, Kale P.1995. Frameshift mutations in *salmonella* induced by the extracts of medicinal herbs *Lannea edulis* (sond.) engl. and *Monotes glaber* Sprague. *Environmental and Molecular Mutagenesis*. **25 (1)**: 77-82.

- Sohnl R, Taysi S, Bakan E, Capoglu I. 1995. Antioxidant status and lipid peroxidation in type 2 diabetes mellitus. *Cell Biochemistry and Function*. **21**:291–296
- Somani R, Kasture S, Singhai AK. 2006. Antidiabetic potential of *Butea monospenna* in rats. *Fitoterapia*. **77**:86-90.
- Srinivasan, K., Suresh Babu, P.. 2005. Influence of dietary capsaicin and onion on the metabolic abnormalities associated with streptozotocin induced diabetes mellitus. *Molecular and Cellular Biochemistry* .**175**: 49-57.
- Sriram, PG, Subramanian, S. 2011. Fisetin, a bioflavonoid ameliorates hyperglycaemia in streptozotocin induced experimental diabetes in rats. *International Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences Review and Research*. **6**: 68-74.
- Standell, E., Decio, E. L., Korsgren, O. and Sandler, S. 1988. Functional characteristics of cultured mouse pancreatic islets following exposure to different streptozotocin concentrations. *Molecular and Cellular Endocrinology*. **59**:83–91
- Starr, C. M. and Hanover, J. A. 1990. Glycosylation of nuclear pore protein p62. Reticulocyte lysate catalyzes O-linked N-acetylglucosamine addition *in vitro*. *Journal of Biological Chemistry*.**265**: 6868–6873
- Sundaram RK, Bhaskar A, Vijayalingam S, Viswanathan M, Mohan R, Shanmugasundaram KR. 1996. Antioxidant status and lipid peroxidation in type 2 diabetes mellitus with and without complications. *Clinical Science (London)*. **90**:255–260
- Szkudelski, T. 2001. The mechanism of alloxan and streptozotocin action β -cells of the rat pancreas. *Physiology Research* .**50**:536-546.

- Takahara, N., Kashiwagi, A., Nishio, Y. 1997. Oxidized lipoproteins found in patients with NIDDM stimulate radical-induced monocyte chemoattractant protein-1 mRNA expression in cultured human endothelial cells. *Diabetologia*. **40**: 662–670.
- Takasu, N., Asawa, T., Komiya, I., Nagasawa, Y., Yama-da, T. 1991. Alloxan induced DNA strand breaks in pancreatic islets. *Journal of Biochemistry*. **266**: 2112-2114.
- Taleb-Contini, SH, Salvador, MJ, Watanabe, E, Ito, I., Oleveira, DCRD. 2003. Antimicrobial activity of flavonoids and steroids isolated from two *Chromolaena* species. *Revista Brasileira de Ciencias Farmaceuticas*. **39**: 403-408.
- Tapas, AR, Sakarkar, DM, Kakde, RB. 2008. Flavonoids as nutraceuticals: A Review. *Tropical Journal of Pharmaceutical Research*. **7**: 1089-1099.
- Tripoli, E, Guardia, ML, Giammanco, S, Majo, DD, Giammanco, M. 2007. Citrus flavonoids: Molecular structure, biological activity and nutritional properties: *A review of food Chemistry*. **104**: 466-479.
- Tsuchiya, H. 2010. Structure-dependent membrane interaction of flavonoids associated with their bioactivity. *Food Chemistry*. **120**: 1089-1096.
- Turk, J., Corbett, J. A., Ramanadham, S., Bohrer, A. and McDaniel, M. L. 1993. Biochemical evidence for nitric oxide formation from streptozotocin in isolated pancreatic islets. *Biochemical and Biophysical Research Communications*. **197**: 1458–1464
- UKPDS. 1998. UK prospective diabetes study 33: intensive blood glucose control with sulphonylureas or insulin compared with conventional treatment and risk of complications with type 2 diabetes. *Lancet* **352**: 837–853.
- Unger, R. H. 1995. Lipotoxicity in the pathogenesis of obesity-dependent NIDDM. *Diabetes*. **44**: 863–870.

- Urban V. S., Kiss J., Kovacs J., Gocza E., Vas V., Monos-tori E., Uher F.2008. Mesenchymal stem cells cooperate with bone marrow cells in therapy of di-abetes. *Stem Cells*. **26**: 244-253
- Veerapur VP, Prabhakar KR, Parihar VP, Kandadi MR, Ramakrishana S. 2009. Ficus racemosa Stem Bark Extract: A Potent Antioxidant and a Probable Natural Radioprotector. *Evidence Based Complement Alternative Medicine*. **6(3)**: 317-324.
- Verna EC, Berk PD.2008. Role of fatty acids in the pathogenesis of obesity and fatty liver: Impact of bariatric surgery. *Seminars in Liver Disease*. **28**:407-426.
- Viana, G.S., Medeiros, A.C., Lacerda, A.M., Leal, L.K., Vale, T.G., Matos, F.J.2004. Hypoglycemic and anti-lipidemic effects of the aqueous extract of *Cissus si-cyoides*. *Biochemical Pharmacology*.**8**: 4-9.
- Vijan, S .2010. "Type 2 diabetes". *Annals of Internal Medicine* 152 (5): ITC31-15.
- Vijayalingam S, Parthiban A, Shanmugasundaram KR, Mohan V. 1996. Abnormal antioxidant status in impaired glucose tolerance and non-insulin-dependent diabetes mellitus. *Diabetes Medicine*. **13**:715–719
- Vimala S, Adenan MI, Ahmad AR, Shahdan R,. 2003. Nature's choice to wellness: Antioxidant vegetables/ulam, Forest Research Institute Malaysia: Selangor.
- Vincent, J.B., 2004. Recent advances in the nutritional biochemistry of trivalent chromium. *Proceedings of the Nutrition Society*. **63**: 41–47.
- Vos T, Flaxman AD, Naghavi M, Lozano R, Michaud C, Ezzati M, Shibuya K, Salomon JA, Abdalla S, Aboyans V. 2012. "Years lived with disability (YLDs) for 1160 sequelae of 289 diseases and injuries 1990–2010: a systematic analysis for the Global Burden of Disease Study 2010." *Lancet* **380**. (9859): 2163–96.

Voss, C., Herrmann, I., Hartmann, K., Zuhlke, H., Besch, W. and Keilacker, H. 1988. Diabetogenic effects of N-nitrosomethylurea in rats. *Experimental and Clinical Endocrinology*. **92**: 25–31.

Wang SY, Jiao H. 2000. Correlation of antioxidant capacities to oxygen radical scavenging enzyme activities in blackberry. *Journal of Agricultural Food Chemistry*.**48**: 5672-5676.

Weiner Z, ben-Shlomo I, beck-Fruchter R, Goldberg y, Shalev E.2011. Clinical and ultrasonographic weight estimation in large for gestational age fetus. *European journal Obstetrics Gynecology Reproduction biology*. 105(1):20-4.

Willi C, Bodenmann P, Ghali WA, Faris PD, Cornuz J. 2007. "Active smoking and the risk of type 2 diabetes: a systematic review and meta-analysis.". *JAMA: the Journal of the American Medical Association* **298** (22): 2654–64.

Williams, RJ, Spencer, JPE, Rice-Evans, C. 2004. Serial review: Flavonoids and isoflavonones (Phytoestrogens): Absorption, Metabolism and Bioactivity. *Free Radical Biology and Medicine*. **36**: 838-849.

Wilson, G. L. and Leiter, E. H.1990. Streptozotocin interactions with pancreatic β -cells and the induction of insulin-dependent diabetes. *Current Topics in Microbiology and Immunology*. **156**: 27–54.

[World Health Organisation](#). 1999. "[Definition, Diagnosis and Classification of Diabetes Mellitus and its Complications](#)" accessed on 12 February, 2015.

WORLD HEALTH ORGANISATION.2013. "[Diabetes Fact sheet N°312](#)". Retrieved 25 March 2015.

WORLD HEALTH ORGANISATION.2013. <http://www.who.int/diabetes/Diabetes Fact sheet N°312>" accessed on February 23, 2015.

World Health Organization (WHO) & International Diabetes Federation (INTERNATIONAL DIABETES FEDERATION). Definition and diagnosis of diabetes mellitus and intermediate hyperglycemia. Geneva: WHO; 2006. Available from:http://www.who.int/diabetes/publications/Definition%20and%20diagnosis%20of%20diabetes_new.pdf assessed 21th February, 2015.

[World Health Organization](#). 2006. [Definition and diagnosis of diabetes mellitus and intermediate hyperglycemia: report of a WHO/INTERNATIONAL DIABETES FEDERATION consultation](#). p. 21.

World Health Organization. 2013. "The top 10 causes of death Fact sheet N°310". Accessed 3rd March, 2015.

Yu F, McGuire PM, Li R, Wang R. 2007. Effects of *Hydrocotyle sibthorpioides* extract on transplanted tumors and immune function in mice, *Phytomedicine*. **14**: 166–171.

Zeiger E, Mutagens that are not carcinogenic: faulty theory or faulty tests?, 2001. *Mutation Research*. **492**: 29-38.

Zheng W, Wang SY. 2001. Antioxidant activity and phenolic compounds in selected herbs. *Journal of Agricultural Food Chemistry*. **49(11)**: 5165-5170.

Zhou, T, Luo, D, Li, X, Luo, Y. 2009. Hypoglycaemic and hypolipidemic effects of flavonoids from lotus (*Nelumbo nucifera*) leaf in diabetic mice. *Journal of Medicinal Plants Research*. **3**: 290-293.